

ZeroPollution4Water Cluster: the overview and the inventory of 32 case studies in drinking and groundwater

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March – 2025

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

European Research Executive Agency (REA)
Unit B.3 — Biodiversity, Circular Economy and Environment

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PDF ISBN: 978-92-95234-46-8 doi:10.2848/3536872 catalogue number : JW-01-25-006-EN-N

Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2025

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Executive Summary

This report aims to provide an overview about the 32 cases studies of seven ZeroPollution4Water Cluster projects. These seven projects received funding under Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme in 2022, aiming to prevent groundwater pollution and secure drinking water quality.

In line with the zero-pollution ambition of the European Green Deal the seven projects are using the case studies to develop and test innovative early-warning systems and treatment solutions to protect water quality, from water sources to drinking water supply. All solutions will address current and future adverse climate change impacts.

The ZeroPollution4Water Cluster currently comprises three groundwater related projects and four drinking water related projects. MAR2PROTECT will provide a holistic approach on managed aquifer recharge in seven coastal case studies, NINFA aims at understanding cumulative stressors and supporting groundwater management in four demo sites and four replication sites, and UPWATER will develop hydrogeological models and novel nature-based solutions (NBS) for decision-making scenarios for two polluted urban and one polluted rural area. H2OforAll, intoDBP, and SafeCREW projects set their focus on tools and technologies to protect drinking water from disinfection by-products (DBP). ToDrinQ aims at treatment plant designs to also minimise per-and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in drinking water.

This Case Study Inventory provides an overview of the projects' case studies. It includes a general description of each case study, highlighting the current state, challenges encountered, and the ambitions for the projects' completion. This serves as a foundation for exploring synergies, strengthening cooperation, and maximising outreach. Covering 32 case studies across 18 countries, the inventory reflects diverse environmental contexts, addresses challenges, and evaluates their impact on catchment areas and water management needs to identify best solutions.

All projects expect or already observed adverse impacts by higher temperatures and more extreme weather events for their case studies. Many of the case studies are impacted by droughts and floods.

All case studies serve to develop and test innovative tools and guidance documents to support better mitigation and prevention of groundwater pollution and management of drinking water supply systems. Improved and more effective monitoring technologies will be developed.

The Case Study Inventory can be used as a basis for the enhanced understanding of new contamination sources, and the deployment of advanced prevention strategies. The case studies are in the process of demonstrating robust risk management techniques and innovative water treatment solutions.

The Case Study Inventory facilitates insights into common features of the case studies as well as in their different contexts and objectives. Exploiting the synergies and differences of the 32 ZeroPollution4Water case studies will increase and consolidate the EU scientific and technological base on measures to manage groundwater and drinking water quality and provide evidence and guidance for policy-making and implementation, particularly concerning the groundwater directive¹, the drinking water directive² and to water resilience related strategies.

¹ [Directive - 2006/118 - EN - EUR-Lex](#), and the EC [Proposal amending Water Directives - European Commission](#)

² [Directive - 2020/2184 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

Acknowledgements

This report was produced by Margarete Remmert-Rieper, member of the Working Group 'Communication' of the ZeroPollution4Water cluster with contribution of the leader of WG 6 Research and Innovation to Impact, a team of co-authors and the case study representatives of each project. The report is the significantly revised version of the first public draft of the [ZeroPollution4Water Cluster Case Study Inventory](#), published 10 July 2024. The ZeroPollution4Water Cluster and the Working Group team would like to acknowledge the European Horizon Europe financial instrument for the financial support.

Disclaimer

The ZeroPollution4Water Cluster comprises seven projects, which have received funding by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The information included herein is legal and true to the best possible knowledge of the authors, as it is the product of the utilisation and synthesis of the referenced sources, for which the authors cannot be held accountable.

Keywords

▪ Case studies ▪ Inventory ▪ Groundwater ▪ Drinking Water ▪ Zero pollution ▪ Prevention and mitigation ▪ Monitoring and treatment ▪ Early-warning systems ▪

1. Introduction

This report aims to provide an overview about the 32 case studies of seven [ZeroPollution4Water Cluster](#) projects. These seven projects have received funding under Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme in 2022³ and aim at preventing groundwater pollution and securing drinking water quality.

In line with the zero-pollution ambition of the European Green Deal⁴ the seven projects will use the case studies to increase the preparedness of the EU water sector for challenges arising from climate change and support EU environmental legislation and policies related to groundwater and drinking water consumer protection. They focus on preventing freshwater pollution, enhancing water quality, and ensuring safe use for both humans and ecosystems, among others. The approach involves the entire drinking water production cycle, with an emphasis on developing innovative and robust monitoring and early-warning systems on drinking water quality, from sources to drinking water supply.

The three projects [MAR2PROTECT](#), [NINFA](#), and [UPWATER](#) provide 18 groundwater related case studies (CS) while the four projects [H2OforALL](#), [intoDBP](#), [SafeCREW](#), and [ToDrinQ](#) work on 14 case studies related to drinking water.

Box 1: The ZeroPollution4Water Cluster

The ZeroPollution4Water cluster is an initiative originated from the coalition of seven different projects from two Horizon Europe call topics aiming at:

- Preventing groundwater contamination and protecting its quality against harmful impacts of global and climate change.
- Securing drinking water quality by protecting water sources against pollution, providing innovative monitoring and treatment solutions, and ensuring safe drinking water distribution.
- Focusing on the European Union's zero-pollution ambition and the European Green Deal, to leverage the cooperation and synergies among these seven projects to develop advanced prevention and mitigation strategies, effective risk assessment and management systems, and innovative monitoring and treatment solutions for drinking water and groundwater management. It also aims to develop new technologies ready for the market to prevent or tackle water pollution.

³ [HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-01](#): Preventing groundwater contamination and protecting its quality against harmful impacts of global and climate change and [HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-04](#): Securing drinking water quality by protecting water sources against pollution, providing innovative monitoring and treatment solutions and ensuring safe distribution

⁴ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *European Green Deal – Research & innovation call*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/33415>

The objectives of the ZeroPollution4Water (ZP4W) Cluster are to:

- **Enhance our understanding** of new contamination sources, pathways, and impacts on water systems. This includes preparing for new challenges through forward-looking research.
- **Develop and deploy advanced strategies** for preventing contamination and mitigating its effects, ensuring the safety of our water sources from global and climate change impacts.
- **Implement robust risk management techniques**, incorporating early-warning systems and decision-support tools for water safety.
- **Innovate in water quality monitoring and treatment**, introducing cost-effective sensors, analytical methods, and treatment technologies (e.g.: nature-based solutions (NBS), advanced disinfection strategies) to ensure source protection and water quality.
- **Support policymaking** with a solid scientific and technological foundation, offering guidance and recommendations for water quality management and further implementation of the European Green Deal.

Six ZP4W Working Groups

- **The Management and Coordination Working Group (WG1)** orchestrates the strategic and operational framework.
- **The Policy Advisory Working Group (WG2)** identifies and develops policy recommendations based on the outcomes of the ZP4W projects.
- **The Communication Working Group (WG3)** engages in amplifying the reach of the outcomes.
- **The Technology and Innovation Working Group (WG4)** seeks to identify, develop, and facilitate the implementation of technology-based solutions.
- **The Data Management and Sharing Working Group (WG5)** aims at devising strategies to elevate data management and sharing.
- **The Research and Innovation to Impact Working Group (WG6)** will facilitate the transition of research and innovation (R&I) to the market uptake in the water sector.

Figure 1: Map of the case studies (credits: Feuga). Black dots: groundwater related case studies. Red dots: drinking water related case studies.).

2. Background and scope

The ZeroPollution4Water Cluster currently comprises three groundwater related projects and four drinking water related projects. Each project targets the expected outcomes of the two Horizon Europe R&I programme 2022 call topics⁵ in a different way and sets different objectives for its case studies. The case studies are characterised by many common features as well as a diversity of approaches and complement each other well.

A brief introduction for each project is given below.

Three groundwater related projects

Three groundwater (GW) related projects (MAR2PROTECT, NINFA, and UPWATER) share a common mission to address critical groundwater challenges in the context of global and climate change. All three projects focus on mitigating pollution, safeguarding groundwater quality, and enhancing resilience against emerging threats such as salinity intrusion, contaminants of emerging concern (CEC), and diffuse agricultural pollution. A brief introduction for each project is given below.

[MAR2PROTECT - Preventing groundwater contamination related to global and climate change through a holistic approach based on managed aquifer recharge](#)

The MAR2PROTECT project is dedicated to addressing significant challenges such as salinity intrusion, groundwater contamination, diffuse agricultural pollution, and emerging contaminants like per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and pharmaceuticals. By adopting a holistic approach, the project aims to prevent groundwater contamination resulting from the impacts of global change and climate change through the application of a new-generation Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR). This approach will be tested in seven case studies across Europe and beyond, focusing on coastal regions in Mediterranean, Atlantic, and North Atlantic climates. The groundwater protection technological and societal engagement approach covers aquifers in diverse contexts, including dunes and surface water and the use of wastewater. The core of this innovative Managed Aquifer Recharge is the M-AI-R Decision Support System that will incorporate technological and societal engagement information. MAR2PROTECT focuses on the prediction of the impacts of global and climate change on groundwater quality, prevention of diffuse pollution from agriculture, development of groundwater management strategies, innovative real-time integrated sensing systems and innovative analytical methods for the monitoring of pollutants.

[NINFA - TakiNg actIoN to prevent and mitigate pollution oF groundwAter bodies](#)

The NINFA project deals with groundwater management solutions in the context of global and climate change. Contaminants of emerging concern like pharmaceuticals, antibiotic resistance genes (ARG), hydrocarbons, heavy metals, and microplastics (MP) infiltrate groundwater from sources, such as wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and urban runoff during storms, impacting interconnected water bodies like rivers, wetlands, and oceans. Although efforts exist to monitor and protect groundwater, gaps remain in understanding cumulative stressors and developing cost-effective monitoring and decision-making tools for sustainable governance and management. NINFA's eight case studies, four test beds

⁵ [HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-01](#): Preventing groundwater contamination and protecting its quality against harmful impacts of global and climate change and [HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-04](#): Securing drinking water quality by protecting water sources against pollution, providing innovative monitoring and treatment solutions and ensuring safe distribution

and four replication sites, offer the opportunity to build a groundwater knowledge observatory to better address these challenges and improve safeguarding groundwater quality and resilience in the face of ongoing environmental changes. Two of the NINFA case study sites are also under the threat of salinity intrusion, and combined effect with pollutants will be considered in a reactive transport groundwater tool for decision support system (DSS) design.

[UPWATER - Understanding groundwater Pollution to protect and enhance WATER quality](#)

The UPWATER project addresses the widespread issue of groundwater pollution by focusing on pollutants such as pesticide wastes, high-load nutrients, ammonium, metals, CECs like PFAS, and pathogens. To address this challenge, the project is identifying effective regulatory and legislative preventive measures and developing cost-efficient methods to measure pollutants, identify their sources and mitigate the pollution. These methods will be validated in three case studies representing different EU climates. Two UPWATER case studies focus on polluted urban areas, while the third targets a polluted rural area. Hydrogeological models and novel nature-based solutions (NBS) for decision-making scenarios shall be developed, which consider multiple stressors and climate change projections. The scale-up of NBS shall be prepared. Policy recommendations target EU as well as local/regional levels, including the update of chemical priority lists.

Four drinking water related projects

Four drinking water related projects, H2OforAll, intoDBP, SafeCREW and ToDrinQ collectively aim to address the evolving challenges posed by climate change, pollution, and the complexities of maintaining high-quality drinking water. These projects focus on safeguarding public health by minimising the risks of contamination from disinfection by-products (DBP), organic pollutants, and emerging contaminants such as PFAS, pesticides, and pathogenic microorganisms. A brief introduction for each project is given below.

[H2OforAll - Innovative Integrated Tools and Technologies to Protect and Treat Drinking Water from Disinfection By-products \(DBPs\)](#)

The H2OforAll project focuses on DBPs that result from the interaction of disinfectants like chlorine with natural organic matter (NOM) in water. Currently, its case study site, the Águas de Coimbra drinking water network, provides high-quality drinking water. However, extreme climate events (floods and droughts) may impact the quality and the complexity of water contamination by CECs such as pharmaceuticals is an arising problem. The case study serves to understand and monitor DBPs and their spread through drinking water distribution systems, to develop breakthrough water treatments to remove DBPs or avoid their formation during water disinfection processes, paying attention to their life cycle analysis, costs, and risks, and to establish preventive measures for water protection engaging public and stakeholders.

[intoDBP - Innovative tools to control organic matter and disinfection by-products in drinking water](#)

The intoDBP project addresses the key challenges of DBP formation, focusing on the deterioration of catchment hydrology and soil biogeochemistry that impacts water quality across all case study sites. High concentrations of dissolved organic matter (DOM) from catchment soils contribute to increased trihalomethane (THM) abundance, a primary DBP. The project aims to develop, test, and scale innovative tools and strategies to minimise human exposure to DBPs without compromising disinfection efficacy. The project will develop its comprehensive approach from source to tap on four case studies combining

rural and dense urban areas, emphasising cost-effective sensors and analytical methods. The case study sites complement each other in terms of the DBP precursors in the source water, the setting, their climate, their current treatment and their disinfection strategy.

SafeCREW - Climate-resilient management for safe disinfected and non-disinfected water supply systems

The SafeCREW project addresses key challenges arising from climate change and increasing water demand, such as potential declines in water availability and quality, high seasonal variations in river surface water, increasing concentration of dissolved organics and microorganisms and the increased migration from relining resins in drinking water systems. To mitigate these challenges, SafeCREW aims to develop risk-based management solutions for both disinfected and non-disinfected water supply. The project will utilise four case studies in northern Germany, Italy, Spain and the Ukraine to improve comprehensive water quality characterisation, develop novel treatment solutions to actively respond to identified threats and guide better management of water distribution networks to maintain high drinking water quality. Novel data sets on the occurrence and concentration of so far unknown DBPs will be created, and commercial actors will be stimulated to further develop tools for DBP quantification and mitigation. This will include all processes from source via treatment and up to distribution.

ToDriQ - TOolkit for aDaptable, Resilient INstallations securing high Quality drinking water

The ToDriQ project tackles the growing concerns of climate change and pollution, particularly from agricultural runoff and pollutants like ammonium, nitrates, pesticides, PFAS, and pathogenic microorganisms. These pollutants threaten drinking water quality, necessitating evidence-based approaches to treatment plant design and enhanced operational awareness across the water system. ToDriQ aims to support the implementation of the revised drinking water directive⁶ (DWD), enhancing scientific and technical knowledge on drinking water quality protection, monitoring, and treatment, increasing the resilience of drinking water systems in terms of both increased robustness and adaptability, and ensuring high-quality drinking water. Five case studies with different environmental and societal contexts shall serve to test and demonstrate the solutions.

The Case Study Inventory – an overview to facilitate insights

This Case Study Inventory serves as an overview to facilitate insights into common challenges and proposed solutions. It presents a general description of each case study including the current challenges and the state of each case study area, and the ambition to overcome them at the end of the project. This will be the starting point to explore the synergetic potential to address common challenges identified by the projects, strengthen the cooperation among the research and innovation solutions in different countries and under different circumstances, and maximise the outreach.

The 32 case studies cover the diversity of environmental contexts with their influence on the situation in the catchment areas and water management needs. **They are situated in 18 countries. Beyond the twelve EU countries represented, case studies are located in western Ukraine, Colombia, Mexico, Tunisia, Egypt, and South Africa. Seventeen case studies centre around the Mediterranean Sea with eight case studies in Spain and three in Portugal** (Fig. 1). With eleven case studies focusing on groundwater pollution, this illustrates the already existing climate related water stress and promises deep insights

⁶ European Commission. Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (recast) (Text with EEA relevance), 2020; Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32020L2184>.

into challenges and zero pollution solutions for the Mediterranean region. The concentration around the Mediterranean region may also enhance the direct transferability of results. Comparing case studies in northern Europe, eastern Europe, the Mediterranean region, South Africa and South America will stimulate the understanding of context-dependent impacts and mutual learning and shall enhance the wide uptake of the results. Learning from the wide country representation also may lead to better adapted water related policies, regulation and legislation regionally, nationally and on the European level.

Case studies in coastal regions show the influence of salinity and floods (NINFA). Case studies in polluted urban areas can be evaluated against study sites in rural environments (e.g. UPWATER, intoDBP). Many case studies already face significant challenges by high pollution and climate change related events (e.g. MAR2PROTECT) whereas other case studies still have a good water quality (SafeCREW CS#1, SafeCREW CS#2, H2OforAll CS#1).

All projects expect or already observe adverse impacts by higher temperatures and more extreme weather events for their case studies. Many of the case study areas are impacted by droughts and floods. Depending on the specific contexts of each case study, this leads to effects such as water scarcity and groundwater depletion, higher concentration of natural organic matter (NOM), salinity, and a wide range of pollutants, including contaminants of emerging concern. A need for increased disinfection of drinking water is expected with higher formation potential of previously unknown DBPs. The aggregation of context-specific analysis of the expected climate change and pollution-related challenges in the case studies on the cluster level will increase data and knowledge exchange as the basis for adaptable and transferable mitigation approaches.

All case studies serve to develop and test innovative tools and guidance documents to support better prevention of groundwater pollution and management of drinking water supply systems. Improved and more effective IT-based monitoring technologies will be developed, including online sensors and predictive modelling approaches. This will enable guidance on risk management and early-warning systems. Novel treatment technologies shall ensure water quality from source to tap and protect human health. Nature-based solutions and managed aquifer recharge approaches will be developed to prevent or remove groundwater pollution. Methods and approaches to prevent the formation of DBPs, to detect previously unknown DBPs, and to remove DBPs effectively will be developed from the data collected at the four drinking water projects. The application of the best practices, collected in case studies, and the evaluation of their market potential, will be discussed during the upcoming months in the ZeroPollution4Water cluster working groups. This will also provide the validated, evidence-based input to water related regulation, e.g. the Groundwater Directive (GWD) (2006/118/EC)⁷ and the Drinking Water Directive (DWD) (EU 2020/2184)⁸, beyond the first policy brief⁹ already published.

⁷ European Commission. Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration. **2006**; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32006L0118>.

⁸ European Commission. Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (recast) (Text with EEA relevance), 2020; Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32020L2184>.

⁹ZeroPollution4Water Cluster. Joint Policy Brief: Preventing groundwater contamination and securing drinking water quality, March 2024. Available at: https://zeropollution4water.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/ZP4W_Deliverable_Policy-Brief-1-3.pdf

Box 2: Key challenges and pollutants currently encountered in the groundwater related case study areas

- Water scarcity and prolonged drought periods increase the concentration of pollutants in groundwater
- Declining groundwater levels and overexploited aquifers due to increasingly common droughts and rising water demand from population and economic growth
- More intensive rainfalls and flash flood phenomena leading to transfer of pollutants such as nitrates, pesticides and nutrients into the groundwater
- Salt intrusion
- Diffuse pollution of groundwater from agriculture (pesticides, nutrients, ammonium, nitrates)
- Contaminants of emerging concern (CEC), such as pharmaceuticals, antibiotic resistance genes (ARG), antibiotic resistant bacteria (ARB), pathogens, hydrocarbons, PFAS, metals, and microplastics from municipal and industrial waste effluents may infiltrate to the groundwater
- Gaps in the understanding of cumulative stressors and impact on interconnected water bodies

To address these challenges, the projects are in the process of developing solutions. Table 1 summarises the location, the type of pollutants in the process to be addressed and the sensing and treatment technologies under evaluation **for each groundwater related case study**.

Table 1 Monitoring technologies and treatment interventions of the groundwater related case studies

Case Study (Country)	Contaminants	Monitoring Technologies		Treatment technologies	
		Hard sensors	Soft Sensors	Nature-based solutions (NBS)	Treatment technologies
MAR2PROTECT CS#1 (Netherlands)	Salinity, turbidity, natural organic matter, particular and colloidal matter		Innovative analytical methods		Coagulation, rapid sand filtration, dissolved air flotation, ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis, adsorption on activated carbon
MAR2PROTECT CS#2 (Tunisia)	Salt intrusion, CEC, Pathogens	Aptasensors for detection of pathogens	DRONE tool to predict GW quality scenarios	Constructed wetlands Phyto-remediation with halophytes	Photovoltaic-powered hybrid nanofiltration/ reverse osmosis Adsorption using local agricultural residues as adsorbents
MAR2PROTECT CS#3 (Portugal)	Pharmaceuticals, PFAS	Chemical-optical sensor for real-time detection of PFAS	REACH tool to predict GW quality and quantity scenarios		Adsorption through biobased materials Aerobic granular sludge bioreactor
MAR2PROTECT CS#4 (Italy)	Pharmaceuticals		DRONE and REACH tools to predict GW quality and quantity scenarios		Adsorption by commercial and innovative adsorbents Membrane aerated biofilm reactor (MABR)
MAR2PROTECT CS#5 (South Africa)	N-based and P-based fertilizers	Real-time sensor for detection of estrogenicity	RAINREC modelling tool to GW artificial recharge REACH tool to predict GW quality and quantity scenarios		FERT ROOT technology to reduce fertilizer leaching
MAR2PROTECT CS#6 (Spain)	Salt intrusion		AI-based DSS DRONE and REACH tools to predict GW quality and quantity scenarios		

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Case Study (Country)	Contaminants	Monitoring Technologies		Treatment technologies	
		Hard sensors	Soft Sensors	Nature-based solutions (NBS)	Treatment technologies
MAR2PROTECT CS#7 (Portugal)	Salt intrusion, Diffuse pollution (nutrients, metals and CEC)		Ecosystem services model	Phytoremediation / re-vegetation with saltmarsh plants	
Ninfa CS#1 (Netherlands)	Nitrate, CEC	Integration of existing sensors and innovative approaches	AI-enhanced hydrological and reactive transport models		
Ninfa CS#2 (Spain)	Salt intrusion, CEC, Nitrates, Nutrients	Multisensory optic-fiber device for measuring groundwater flow, salinity, nitrates, etc.		Woodchip reactor and electrowetland	Membrane-based and advanced oxidation processes
Ninfa CS#3 (Spain)	Urban runoff			Green tile, Sustainable Drainage Systems (SUDS)	Membrane-based and advanced oxidation processes
Ninfa CS#4 (France)	CEC, ARB/ARG			Biofiltration	Advanced oxidation processes Adsorption with activated carbon
Ninfa CS#5 (Spain)	Salt infiltration	<i>Replication site: Monitoring to create Groundwater Knowledge Observatory and contribute to NINFA DSS</i>			
Ninfa CS#6 (Colombia)	CEC, ARG, Microplastics	<i>Replication site: Monitoring to create Groundwater Knowledge Observatory and contribute to NINFA DSS</i>			
Ninfa CS#7 (Mexico)	CEC, ARG, Microplastics	<i>Replication site: Monitoring to create Groundwater Knowledge Observatory and contribute to NINFA DSS</i>			
Ninfa CS#8 (Egypt)	CEC, ARG, Microplastics	<i>Replication site: Monitoring to create Groundwater Knowledge Observatory and contribute to NINFA DSS</i>			

Case Study (Country)	Contaminants	Monitoring Technologies		Treatment technologies	
		Hard sensors	Soft Sensors	Nature-based solutions (NBS)	Treatment technologies
UPWATER CS#1 (Denmark)	CEC (pesticides), metals	Ceramic passive samplers measuring CEC Diffusive gradients in thin films measuring trace metals		Moving bed bioreactor (MBBR) Biofiltration	Microbial degradation Plant uptake, adsorption to sand
UPWATER CS#2 (Greece)	CEC PFAS PAH Metals Pathogens	Ceramic passive samplers measuring CEC Virus passive samplers Diffusive gradients in thin films measuring trace metals Realtime sensors measuring electrical conductivity, chemical oxygen demand (COD), temperature, level of the groundwater table, etc.	Source apportionment-modelling	Bioelectrochemical wetlands Shallow-infiltration well	Plant uptake, microbial degradation, adsorption microbial degradation, adsorption
UPWATER CS#3 (Spain)	CEC PFAS Metals Pathogens	Ceramic passive samplers measuring CEC Virus passive samplers Diffusive gradients in thin films measuring trace metals Realtime sensors measuring electrical conductivity, COD, temperature, level of the groundwater table, etc.	Source apportionment-modelling	Floating root mats plus bioelectrochemical wetlands	Plant uptake, microbial degradation, adsorption

Box 3: Key challenges currently encountered in the case study areas of drinking water

- Deterioration of drinking water quality due to climate change impacts in the water source as well as in the distribution networks.
- High seasonal variations and complexity of source water pollution by e.g. pharmaceuticals, PFAS, ammonium, nitrates, pesticides (agricultural runoff), and bacterial contamination, dependent on the local conditions of water catchment areas and drinking water distribution systems
- Increased natural organic matter (NOM) as potential DBP precursors due to rising temperatures and extreme weather events, especially in surface water as drinking water source
- Risks to human health due to increased concentrations of algal blooms in surface water
- Increased growth of bacteria in extended drinking water distribution networks might result in increased disinfection needs and enhanced DBP generation
- Largely unknown interaction of disinfectants with DBP precursors like NOM or pipe materials, the potential incidence of a wide range of DBPs beyond THM, including polar DBPs, i-DBPs and n-DBPs
- Lack of risk assessment methodologies and early-warning systems to adapt water treatment and disinfection processes
- Old pipelines in the distribution network
- Difficulty on monitoring the real concentration of DBPs along the distribution network
- Lack of technologies to remove DBPs from water

To address these challenges, the projects are in the process of developing solutions. Table 2 summarises the location and the targeted monitoring and treatment systems in the drinking water related case-studies. **The main aim of all projects is to reduce the incidence of DBPs in drinking water** by following different approaches: improving the water quality monitoring to optimise the treatment trains; developing suitable treatments to remove DBP precursors from the source; defining novel disinfection strategies or removing DBPs from drinking water.

Table 2 Monitoring technologies and treatment interventions of the drinking water related case studies

Case Study (County)	Monitoring Technologies ¹⁰		Treatment technologies & treatment interventions	
	Hard sensors	Soft Sensors	Treatment technologies	Treatment interventions
H2OforAll CS#1 (Portugal)	Spectroscopic methods combined with auxiliary sensors	Hydraulic models with water quality parameters (WQP) Algorithm for intelligent placement of sensing infrastructure	Source water treatment: Advanced oxidation processes (AOP) for DBP precursor removal Novel materials for DBP adsorption	UV combined with intermittent chlorination (to reduce amount of chlorine)
IntoDBP CS#1 (Cyprus)	Fluoro-absorbance sensors; Bioreporters; UV-VIS sensors	Hydraulic modelling for DBP fate estimation	MITO3X® pilot plant for pre-oxidization optimisation	Upgrade water treatment trains in drinking water treatment plants (DWTP)
IntoDBP CS#2 (Spain)	Fluoro-absorbance sensors; Bioreporters; UV-VIS sensors	Hydraulic modelling for DBP fate estimation	MITO3X® pilot plant for pre-oxidization optimisation	Upgrade DWTP water treatment trains; Develop risk assessment methodology for DBP formation
IntoDBP CS#3 (Spain)	UV-VIS sensors		MITO3X® pilot for chloramine disinfection optimisation	
IntoDBP CS#4 (Ireland)	UV-VIS; Fluorescence	Algorithms to predict DBP formation	Catchment-based source protection measures	Develop risk assessment methodology for DBP formation
SafeCREW CS#1 (Germany)	High volume sampling for microbial contamination and continuous flow cytometry		Porous conductive membrane for NOM removal	Improved quantitative microbial risk assessment methods; Strategies to provide safe DW with minimal DBPs, (considering potential reactions between residuals in the currently non-disinfected DWDN)
SafeCREW CS#2 (Italy)	Passive sampler for effective microbial monitoring; Characterisation of DBPs by interaction with relining resins in DWDN	Soft sensors: online bacterial load measurement; Advanced data computing and prediction of DBP formation	Cellulosic nanosponges as novel adsorption materials for removal of DBP and DBP precursors	Early-warning system and integrated risk assessment weighing pathogens and DBP; Optimisation of disinfection operating parameters and relining materials

¹⁰ Pollutants addressed: H2OforAll, intoDBP and SafeCREW focus on NOM (including microorganisms) and DBP (including THM and novel DBPs), while ToDriQ addresses a wider range of contaminants of emerging concern.

ZeroPollution4Water Cluster: the overview and the inventory of 32 case studies in drinking and groundwater

Case Study (County)	Monitoring Technologies ¹⁰		Treatment technologies & treatment interventions	
	Hard sensors	Soft Sensors	Treatment technologies	Treatment interventions
SafeCREW CS#3 (Spain)		Online THM analyser (with differentiation of THMs); Soft sensors for DWTP and DWDN to model DBP target parameters; In-network DBP formation prediction model	Combination of different AOP techniques for optimal settings for transformation of DBP precursors	Early alert system and risk assessment tool for optimising NOM removal and chlorination boosting in the network; Optimal risk-based and cost-efficient management of the DWTP and DWDN combining chemical, toxicity and microbial risk in one performance indicator set.
SafeCREW CS#4 (Ukraine)		Replication site: hydraulic models and soft sensors to predict spatial and temporal chlorine and DBP		Implementing risk-based management through the creation of Water Safety Plans (WSP)
ToDriQ CS#1 (Netherlands)	Ammonium analysis; Lead determination; Online flow cytometer; Total cells count	Short-term forecasting of turbidity; Estimation model to optimise ozonation	Cost-efficient PFAS adsorption process	Design-support tool for alternative treatment trains for different types of water sources and raw water quality; Modular platform to advise on optimal control and risk management interventions throughout the water supply chain
ToDriQ CS#2 (Greece)	Nitrates; Ammonium; Bacterial load; <i>E. Coli</i>	Chlorophyll-a Water quality Predictive models for algal blooms	New water treatment unit optimised using the sensing data, testing MABR technology	Design-support tool for efficient water treatment plant operation
ToDriQ CS#3 (Switzerland)	Bactosense; Udetect	Real-time monitoring		Implementing automated systems for continuous monitoring and rapid response to potential incidents
ToDriQ CS#4 (France)	IonSens; MetalSens; BactoSense; Udetect		-	
ToDriQ CS#5 (Czechia)	Off-line analysers for anions and metals	Development of online analysers	-	

The two tables and the elaborations above show how the Case Study Inventory can be used as a basis for the enhanced understanding of new contamination sources, the deployment of advanced prevention strategies, and for providing a solid scientific and technological foundation for policy making. The case studies are in the process of demonstrating robust risk management techniques and innovative water treatment solutions, and thus fully support the objectives of the ZeroPollution4Water Cluster¹¹. The case studies will contribute to the EU Green Deal initiative¹² actions increasing water resilience in Europe.

¹¹ ZeroPollution4Water Cluster. Strategy and Vision, December 2024. Available at: <https://zeropollution4water.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/ZP4W-Cluster-StrategyVision.pdf>

¹² European Commission. Communication from the Commission: The European Green Deal. Brussels: 2019; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1588580774040&uri=CELEX:52019DC0640>.

3. Groundwater related case studies

3.1. MAR2PROTECT case studies

MAR2PROTECT includes seven case studies which are presented below:

- Case study 1 - Katwijk, Netherlands
- Case study 2 - Nabeul, Tunisia
- Case study 3 - Frielas, Portugal
- Case Study 4 - Emilia-Romagna, Italy
- Case Study 5 - Cape Flats, South Africa
- Case Study 6 - Marbella, Spain
- Case Study 7 - Lima River Estuary, Portugal

3.1.1. MAR2PROTECT Case Study 1- Katwijk, Netherlands

MAR2PROTECT CS#1 - Katwijk, Netherlands	
	<p>Tertiary treatment of lake water and subsequent managed aquifer recharge of a dunal aquifer affected by salinity intrusion</p>
<p>Location</p>	<p>Katwijk, Netherlands</p>
<p>Pictures illustrating the case studies</p>	<div data-bbox="683 667 1203 1167" data-label="Image"> </div> <p data-bbox="580 1205 1305 1234"><i>Figure 3.1.1.1 Demosite 1. MAR2PROTECT Location Map (© FEUGA 2022)</i></p> <div data-bbox="475 1323 1422 1653" data-label="Image"> </div> <p data-bbox="687 1688 1203 1718"><i>Figure 3.1.1.2 Dunea Katwijk plant (© S.Salinas 2022)</i></p>
<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Groundwater, surface water treatment, salinity intrusion, micropollutants, managed aquifer recharge (MAR).</p>
<p>Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges</p>	<p>As a result of climate change, the Lake Valkenburg water is increasingly affected by high salinity.</p>

MAR2PROTECT CS#1 - Katwijk, Netherlands	
	<p>Due to the rapidly increasing water demand from population and economic growth, the water utility Dunea needs to start drawing surface water from Lake Valkenburg before infiltration in the Berkheide dunal aquifer.</p>
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pilot plant has been set up at the onset of MAR2PROTECT, and it has been in operation for over 1 year with very positive results in terms of removal of the main (micro)pollutants, with no indications of membrane fouling. The final adsorption step with activated carbon was not validated yet.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Managed Aquifer Recharge using water from the nearby Lake Valkenburg has been identified as the best strategy for long-term aquifer protection and preservation. Fed by the river Old Rhine, it is increasingly contaminated by salinity (salt intrusion from the sea) and micropollutants. Therefore, treatment of the lake water is needed in order to prevent groundwater contamination resulting from Managed Aquifer Recharge. To this goal, Dunea and the IHE Delft Institute set up a membrane-based lake water treatment process in a 15 m³/h pilot plant, where different combinations of inline coagulation, rapid sand filtration, ultrafiltration and reverse osmosis are being tested.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a cost-efficient surface water treatment before it is used for managed aquifer recharge and eventually for drinking water production. Assessment of two alternative treatment lines at a demonstration scale (15 m³/h). Development and validation of innovative monitoring methods for the assessment and early detection of fouling phenomena in ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis and sand filtration systems.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>Dunea and IHE Delft designed and installed a pilot plant treating 15 m³/h of surface water. The pilot plant is articulated in 2 lines, aimed at comparing two alternative treatment approaches:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Coagulation/flocculation + dissolved air flotation + ultrafiltration + reverse osmosis 2) Coagulation/flocculation + dissolved air flotation + rapid sand filtration + adsorption on activated carbon <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 10px;"> <pre> graph TD VL[Valkenburg lake] --> CF[Coagulation/Flocculation] CF --> DAF[DAF] DAF --> RSF[RSF] DAF --> UF[UF] RSF --> GAC[GAC filtration] UF --> RO[RO] subgraph DashedBox [] UF RO end </pre> </div>

Figure 3.1.1.3 Schematic of pretreatment lines in Demosite 1 (© Vanida Salgado 2024)

MAR2PROTECT CS#1 - Katwijk, Netherlands	
	<p>Replication potential: The proposed technologies for surface water treatment have a very high potential for replication across Europe, given the high number of sites in which surface water contaminated by salinity and micropollutants are used for managed aquifer recharge and/or drinking water production.</p>
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A cost-efficient treatment of surface water before it is used for managed aquifer recharge and eventually for drinking water production, validated at demonstration scale.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of analytical methods for biological and particulate fouling. • Bacterial growth potential based on adenosine-triphosphate (ATP) method for freshwater and Modified Fouling Index -0.45 (MFI- 0.45) and Modified Fouling Index - Ultrafiltration (MFI-UF).
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation at demonstration scale of a cost-efficient treatment of surface water before it is used for managed aquifer recharge and eventually for drinking water production. • Validation of innovative monitoring methods for the assessment and early detection of fouling phenomena in ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis and sand filtration systems. • Assessment of the proposed technologies, enhancement of their replication potential and implementation of civil society engagement activities, through the involvement of a large stakeholder community by means of a LivingLab based on this case study. <p>Beyond the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the replication of the selected surface water treatment sequence in other regions facing similar surface water and climate challenges. • Increase the awareness of civil society groups on the issues of water scarcity and groundwater protection.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC: Establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater. • Groundwater Directive (GWD) 2006/118/EC: Establishes specific measures as provided for in Article 17(1) and (2) of Directive 2000/60/EC in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution.
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results of the proposed technologies for surface water treatment could be used to develop policy recommendations and national legislation on the use of surface water for managed aquifer recharge.
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market placement of the best-performing treatment sequence for the treatment of surface water before its use for managed aquifer recharge and drinking water production.

3.1.2. MAR2PROTECT Case Study 2 - Nabeul, Tunisia

MAR2PROTECT CS#1 - Nabeul, Tunisia	
	Tertiary treatment of municipal wastewater and subsequently managed aquifer recharge of an over-exploited coastal aquifer affected by micropollutants and saline intrusion
Location	Oued Souhil, Tunisia
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p><i>Figure 3.1.2.2 Demosite 2 (ISSBAT 2024)</i></p>

MAR2PROTECT CS#1 - Nabeul, Tunisia	
Keywords	Wastewater treatment, salinity intrusion, micropollutants, managed aquifer recharge, nature-based solutions and sensors.
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	As a result of climate change and population growth, groundwater level is rapidly declining and water quality is deteriorating due to seawater intrusion (total salinity reaching 7 g/L) and diffuse pollution from agriculture (pesticides, fertilizers).
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The above-listed wastewater treatment technologies are being assessed in lab-scale tests, with promising results. • The scale-up of technologies at TRL 5 in the demosite is planned for May 2025. • The case study LivingLab has been launched, and civil society engagement activities have been designed.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>The 330 km² Oued Souhil aquifer, located in the Cap Bon Peninsula in Tunisia, is strongly overexploited due to increasing water demand for domestic use and irrigation. GW level is rapidly declining and water quality is deteriorating due to seawater intrusion (total salinity reaching 7 g/L) and diffuse pollution from agriculture (pesticides, fertilizers). In response, the local basin authority started aquifer recharge operations with treated municipal wastewater (MWW) from two WWTPs SE3 (oxidation ditches) and SE4 (activated sludge). using 4 infiltration basins (737 m²). This method was used irregularly until 2010 then was abandoned and replaced by irrigation as an indirect method of aquifer recharge. Treated MWW from the SE3 and SE4 WWTPs is polluted by high salinity, some pathogens and micropollutants at low concentrations. There is thus a strong need to implement an effective tertiary treatment at the SE3 and SE4 WWTPs, to minimise the introduction of these pollutants in the aquifer.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a cost-efficient advanced treatment of secondary-treated wastewater before it is used for managed aquifer recharge and irrigation. • Development and validation of an innovative aptasensor for the real-time detection of pathogen bacteria in groundwater and wastewater. • Development and implementation of an innovative methodology to establish LivingLabs across MAR2PROTECT case studies. • Organization of LivingLab activities addressed to engage stakeholders, establish LivingLab teams and co-design broader societal engagement interventions across the MAR2PROTECT case studies.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>The Higher Institute of Applied Biological Sciences of Tunis - University of Tunis El-Manar, the leader of this case study, is developing several technologies for the advanced treatment of municipal wastewater before its use for aquifer recharge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constructed wetlands, as tertiary treatment of treated wastewater. • Low-cost selective adsorption of selected micropollutants (diclofenac, bisphenol A and ofloxacin) using locally available agricultural residues, and treatment of the saturated sorbents with ligninolytic fungi. • Photovoltaic-powered hybrid nanofiltration / reverse osmosis process for salt and micropollutant removal from treated wastewater and brine phytoremediation with halophytes.

MAR2PROTECT CS#1 - Nabeul, Tunisia	
	The proposed technologies for advanced wastewater treatment before its use for MAR have a high replication potential, given the high potential of managed aquifer recharge with treated wastewater.
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A cost-efficient advanced treatment of secondary-treated wastewater before it is used for managed aquifer recharge and irrigation, validated at TRL5 in a real environment. • A robust aptasensor for the detection of pathogen bacteria in groundwater and wastewater.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constructed wetlands (current TRL5 / expected TRL7). • Low-cost selective adsorption of selected micropollutants (current TRL4 / expected TRL6). • Treatment of the saturated sorbents by solid-state fermentation with ligninolytic fungi (current TRL3 / expected TRL4). • Aptasensors for detection of pathogens (current TRL3 / expected TRL5).
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation at TRL 5 of a cost-efficient treatment of secondary-treated wastewater before it is used for managed aquifer recharge and irrigation. • Validation of a robust aptasensor for the detection of pathogen bacteria in groundwater and wastewater. • Assessment of the proposed technologies, enhancement of their replication potential and implementation of civil society engagement activities, through the involvement of a large stakeholder community by means of a LivingLab based on this case study. <p>Beyond the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the replication of the selected wastewater treatment sequence in other regions facing similar surface water and climate challenges. • Implementation of the aptasensor for the detection of pathogen bacteria in different types of wastewater. • Increase the awareness of civil society groups on the issues of water scarcity and groundwater protection.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>EU legislation not applicable. This case study is located in Africa.</p> <p>Tunisian national policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Code of 1975. • Decree No. 78-814 laying down the conditions for the exploration and exploitation of groundwater.
Policy implications	The results of the proposed technologies for wastewater treatment and monitoring could be used to formulate policy recommendations relative to guidelines and national legislation on the use of treated wastewater for MAR.
Market implications	<p>Market placement of the best-performing technologies for the treatment of wastewater before its use for managed aquifer recharge and irrigation.</p> <p>Market placement of the aptasensor for the detection of pathogen bacteria in wastewater and groundwater.</p>

3.1.3. MAR2PROTECT Case Study 3 - Frielas, Portugal

MAR2PROTECT CS#3 - Frielas, Portugal	
	Treatment of municipal wastewater effluent of an over-exploited coastal aquifer affected by micropollutants and saline intrusion
Location	Frielas, Portugal
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<div style="text-align: center;"><p><i>Figure 3.1.3.2. Frielas wastewater treatment plant</i> (https://www.aquasdoejoatlantico.adp.pt/noticias/comunicado-retomada-operacao-na-fabrica-de-agua-de-frielas)</p></div>
Keywords	Wastewater treatment, salinity intrusion, PFAS, pharmaceuticals, managed aquifer recharge (MAR), monitoring technologies, real-time sensors, online monitoring, modelling, digital tools, and novel treatment technologies.

MAR2PROTECT CS#3 - Frielas, Portugal	
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	As a result of climate change and population growth, groundwater levels are rapidly declining and water quality is deteriorating due to seawater intrusion.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The above-listed wastewater treatment technologies are being assessed in lab-scale tests, with promising results. • The scale-up of technologies at TRL5 in the demosite is planned for May 2025. • The case study LivingLab has been launched, and civil society engagement activities have been designed.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Frielas WWTP belongs to AdTA and is linked to the West edge, Tagus alluvium, and Tagus-Sado basin (left bank) aquifers, affected by relevant salt intrusion. This WWTP discharges treated effluent into the Tagus basin and treats 70,000 m³/day. The quaternary treatment to remove emerging contaminants is currently not applied, and some PFAS and pharmaceuticals were detected in the effluent. The discharge of these emerging pollutants, expected to increase with population and industrialisation rise, can have a serious impact on managed aquifer recharge implementation and acceptance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a cost-efficient advanced treatment of secondary-treated wastewater before it is used for managed aquifer recharge. • Development and validation of an innovative optical sensor for the real-time detection of PFAS in different types of water sources. • Development and implementation of an innovative methodology to establish LivingLabs across MAR2PROTECT case studies. • Organisation of LivingLab activities addressed to engage stakeholders, establish LivingLab teams and co-design broader societal engagement interventions across the MAR2PROTECT case studies.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>NOVA University Lisbon, the leader of this case study, is developing several technologies for the advanced treatment of municipal wastewater before its use for aquifer recharge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Removal of micropollutants (PFAS, pharmaceuticals) by adsorption on innovative biobased materials. • Biodegradation of pharmaceuticals in an aerobic granular sludge bioreactor, combined with the concentration of pharmaceuticals by means of aqueous biphasic systems. • Removal of gas-phase GHGs produced by the biodegradation process, using adsorption on innovative biobased materials.

MAR2PROTECT CS#3 - Frielas, Portugal

Figure 3.1.3.3. Flowsheet of the combined process proposed by NOVA for DS3, Frielas, Portugal.

Replication potential:

- The water treatment technology object of this case study has a very high replication potential, given the widespread presence of the target micropollutants in wastewater across Europe.
- The PFAS real-time sensor has a very high replication potential, given the increasing concern and the rapid legislative framework relative to the removal and monitoring of PFAS in different types of water sources.

Expected outcomes

- A cost-efficient advanced treatment of secondary-treated wastewater before it is used for managed aquifer recharge and irrigation, validated at TRL 5 in a real environment.
- A robust optical sensor for the real-time detection of PFAS in different types of water sources.

Key technologies and deployment (TRL)

- Micropollutant adsorption on biobased materials (current TRL 3/ expected TRL 5).
- Micropollutant biodegradation process based on aerobic granular sludge (AGS) bioreactors (current TRL 3/ expected TRL 4).
- PFAS sensor (current TRL 3/ expected TRL 5).

Ambition at the end of the project and beyond

- Validation at TRL 5 of a cost-efficient treatment of secondary-treated wastewater before it is used for managed aquifer recharge.
- Validation of a robust optical sensor for the real-time detection of PFAS in different types of water sources.
- Assessment of the proposed technologies, enhancement of their replication potential and implementation of civil society engagement activities, through the involvement of a large stakeholder community by means of a LivingLab based on this case study

Beyond the project:

- Facilitate the replication of the selected wastewater treatment process in other regions facing similar wastewater effluent and climate challenges.
- Implementation of the optical sensor for the real-time detection of PFAS in different types of water sources.

MAR2PROTECT CS#3 - Frielas, Portugal	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the awareness of civil society groups on the issues of water scarcity and groundwater protection.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC: Establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater. • Groundwater Directive 2006/118/EC: Establishes specific measures as provided for in Article 17(1) and (2) of Directive 2000/60/EC in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution. • Lei da Água n.o 58/2005 (Water Law) (Portugal): https://files.dre.pt/1s/2005/12/249a00/72807310.pdf.
Policy implications	<p>The results of the proposed technologies for wastewater treatment and monitoring could be used to formulate policy recommendations relative to guidelines and national legislation on the use of treated wastewater for MAR.</p>
Market implications	<p>Market placement of the best-performing technologies for the treatment of wastewater before its use for managed aquifer recharge.</p> <p>Market placement of the optical sensor for the real-time detection of PFAS in different types of water sources.</p>

3.1.4. MAR2PROTECT Case Study 4 - Emilia-Romagna, Italy

MAR2PROTECT CS#4 - Emilia-Romagna, Italy	
	Managed recharge of a coastal aquifer, using treated municipal wastewater
Location	Emilia Romagna, Italy
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 3.1.4.2 Implementation of the DRONE modelling tool to Demosite 4: simulation of future salinity intrusion in the Ravenna coastal aquifer. ©: University of Bologna</i></p>
Keywords	Wastewater treatment, salinity intrusion, micropollutants, managed aquifer recharge (MAR), micropollutant biodegradation, zero pollution, groundwater, treatment technologies, and modelling.

MAR2PROTECT CS#4 - Emilia-Romagna, Italy	
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	As a result of climate change and population growth, groundwater levels are declining and water quality is deteriorating due to seawater intrusion.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The above-listed wastewater treatment technologies are being assessed in lab-scale tests, with promising results. The scale-up of technologies at TRL 5 in the demosite is planned for May 2025. The case study LivingLab has been launched, and civil society engagement activities have been designed.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>The Ravenna coastal aquifer (Emilia-Romagna) is affected by overexploitation, relevant saline intrusion (3-20 g/L), and diffuse pollution from agriculture. Climate change and increasing water abstraction due to increasing population and agricultural production are expected to increase these problems. Managed aquifer recharge with treated wastewater (WW) from coastal WWTPs has been identified as a promising solution to ensure long-term sustainable management of the aquifer. Preliminary investigations revealed the presence of pharmaceuticals in the effluents of investigated coastal WWTPs. A tertiary treatment of the selected WWTP effluents is thus necessary, to remove the identified pollutants and protect the Ravenna coastal aquifer.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of a cost-efficient advanced treatment of secondary-treated wastewater before it is used for managed aquifer recharge. Development of an innovative modelling tool (DRONE) for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems, taking into account climate change scenarios and the use of multiple water sources. Development and implementation of an innovative methodology to establish LivingLabs across MAR2PROTECT case studies. Organisation of LivingLab activities addressed to engage stakeholders, establish LivingLab teams and co-design broader societal engagement interventions across the MAR2PROTECT case studies.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>Bologna University, the leader of this case study, is developing several technologies for the advanced treatment of municipal wastewater before its use for aquifer recharge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Removal of micropollutants (pharmaceuticals) by adsorption on commercial and innovative sorbents (molecularly imprinted polymers). Biodegradation of the desorbed pharmaceuticals in a membrane aerated biofilm reactor (MABR). <p>The flow sheet of the proposed treatment sequence is reported below.</p>

MAR2PROTECT CS#4 - Emilia-Romagna, Italy

Figure 3.1.4.3. Flow-sheet of the integrated adsorption / biodegradation process for the removal of pharmaceuticals from effluents of wastewater treatment plants, before their re-use for aquifer recharge. Source: University of Bologna.

In addition, Bologna University is developing an innovative modelling tool (DRONE) for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems, taking into account climate change scenarios and the use of multiple water sources.

Replication potential:

- The water treatment technologies object of this case study has a very high replication potential, given the widespread presence of the target micropollutants in wastewater across Europe.
- The DRONE modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems has a very high replication potential, given the need to boost managed aquifer recharge and to design it taking into account future climate change scenarios.

Expected outcomes

- A cost-efficient advanced treatment of secondary-treated wastewater before it is used for managed aquifer recharge and irrigation, validated at TRL 5 in a real environment.
- An innovative modelling tool (DRONE) for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems, taking into account climate change scenarios and the use of multiple water sources.

Key technologies and deployment (TRL)

- Fixed-bed adsorption: expected TRL at end of project = 5.
- Biodegradation in a Membrane Aerated Biofilm Reactor (MABR): expected TRL at end of project = 4.

Ambition at the end of the project and beyond

- Validation at TRL 5 in a real environment of a cost-efficient treatment of secondary-treated wastewater before it is used for managed aquifer recharge.
- Validation in a real environment of an innovative modelling tool (DRONE) for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems, taking into account climate change scenarios and the use of multiple water sources.

MAR2PROTECT CS#4 - Emilia-Romagna, Italy	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of the proposed technologies, enhancement of their replication potential and implementation of civil society engagement activities, through the involvement of a large stakeholder community by means of a LivingLab based on this case study. <p>Beyond the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate the replication of the selected wastewater treatment process in other regions facing similar water and climate challenges. Implementation of the DRONE modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems in aquifers characterised by similar contexts. Increase the awareness of civil society groups on the issues of water scarcity and groundwater protection.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC: Establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater. Groundwater Directive 2006/118/EC: Establishes specific measures as provided for in Article 17(1) and (2) of Directive 2000/60/EC in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution. Government Decree 100/2016 on Managed Aquifer Recharge (Italy). Draft of Government Decree under discussion, on the reuse of wastewater including managed aquifer recharge (Italy).
Policy implications	<p>The MAR2PROTECT activities developed in this case study can contribute to the ongoing discussion on the draft of the Government Decree, relative to the reuse of wastewater including managed aquifer recharge.</p>
Market implications	<p>Market placement of the best-performing technologies for the treatment of wastewater before its use for managed aquifer recharge.</p> <p>Market placement of the DRONE modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems, taking into account climate change scenarios and the use of multiple water sources.</p>

3.1.5. MAR2PROTECT Case Study 5 - Cape Flats, South Africa

MAR2PROTECT CS#5 - Cape Flats, South Africa	
	<p>Use of tertiary treated MWW for the managed aquifer recharge of a coastal aquifer affected by saline intrusion and diffuse pollution from agriculture</p>
<p>Location</p>	<p>Cape Flats, South Africa</p>
<p>Pictures illustrating the case studies</p>	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p><i>Figure 3.1.5.2 Map created using QGIS V3.34.2.</i></p> </div>
<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Wastewater treatment, salinity intrusion, micropollutants, managed aquifer recharge, soil health, estrogenicity and real-time biosensors.</p>
<p>Current status of the case study:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The FERTilizer use reduction through ROOT health enhancement (FERT ROOT) technology is being assessed in both lab-scale and field tests, with promising results. • The real-time sensor based on receptor-binding assays for the detection of estrogenicity is under development at laboratory scale. • The RAINfall-runoff RECharge re-distribution tool (RAINREC) modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems and the assessment of runoff-recharge interactions is under development and calibration.

MAR2PROTECT CS#5 - Cape Flats, South Africa	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The case study LivingLab will be launched during the second half of 2024 and civil society engagement activities have been designed.
Expected outcomes	<p>A cost-efficient technology to reduce fertilizer leaching into aquifers, validated at TRL 5 in a real environment (FERT ROOT).</p> <p>The innovative RAINREC modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems and the assessment of runoff-recharge interactions, taking into account climate change scenarios.</p>
Key intervention and objectives	<p>The 400 km² Cape Flats Aquifer (CFA) is the major source of municipal water for Cape Town City (9 Mm³/y) and irrigation (200 ktons vegetables/y). CFA is increasingly contaminated by salinity intrusion and diffuse pollution from agriculture and micropollutants. The current GW extraction rate is at 100% of natural recharge and seawater intrusion is increasing. Due to climate change and the rapid increase in population (+56% in 6 years) and food production, CFA is expected to reach oversaturation during the next 5 years. A preliminary MAR project with treated MWW is starting to be developed at basin level, to increase the CFA recharge rate and curb salinity intrusion. Preliminary monitoring of the effluent of the Cape Town Athlon WWTP indicated emerging pollutants, with a risk of transfer into the aquifer. A wider monitoring of pollutants by means of real-time sensors is needed, also to design suitable tertiary treatments to be implemented before the WW is used for MAR. To ensure a gradual improvement of CFA water quality, MAR needs to be associated with preventive measures aimed at decreasing diffuse pollution from agriculture.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of a cost-efficient real-time biosensor based on receptor-binding assays for the detection of estrogenicity in wastewater and groundwater. Development of the FERT-ROOT technology to reduce fertilizer leaching into aquifers. Development of the innovative RAINREC modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems and the assessment of runoff-recharge interactions, taking into account climate change scenarios. Development and implementation of an innovative methodology to establish LivingLabs across MAR2PROTECT case studies. Organisation of LivingLab activities addressed to engage stakeholders, establish LivingLab teams and co-design broader societal engagement interventions across the MAR2PROTECT case studies.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>Stellenbosch University, the leader of this case study, is developing several technologies and modelling tools for the sustainable management of groundwater and the design of managed aquifer recharge in the Cape Flats aquifer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A real-time sensor based on receptor-binding assays for the detection of estrogenicity in wastewater and groundwater. The FERT-ROOT technology to reduce fertilizer leaching into aquifers. The innovative RAINREC modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems and the assessment of runoff-recharge interactions, taking into account climate change scenarios.

MAR2PROTECT CS#5 - Cape Flats, South Africa	
	<p>Replication potential:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The FERT-ROOT technology to reduce fertilizer leaching into aquifers has a high replication potential, given the widespread eutrophication issues in aquifers. • The real-time estrogenicity sensor has a high replication potential, given the widespread presence of endocrine disruptors in groundwater and wastewater. • The RAINREC modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems has a high replication potential, given the high need for MAR systems in African countries.
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<p>As a result of climate change and population growth, groundwater level is declining and water quality is deteriorating due to seawater intrusion.</p>
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online real-time estrogenicity biosensor (current TRL3/ expected TRL5) • FERT-ROOT mitigation of fertilizer leaching (current TRL5/ expected TRL7).
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of novel deployable online real-time estrogenicity sensor for future use for monitoring of effluents, groundwater and surface water by the public and private sectors. • Validation at TRL 5 in a real environment of a cost-efficient technology to reduce fertilizer leaching into aquifers. • Validation in a real environment of the innovative RAINREC modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems and the assessment of runoff-recharge interactions, taking into account climate change scenarios. • Assessment of the proposed technologies, enhancement of their replication potential and implementation of civil society engagement activities, through the involvement of a large stakeholder community by means of a LivingLab based on this case study. <p>Beyond the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the replication of the FERT-ROOT technology to reduce fertilizer leaching into aquifers, in other regions facing aquifer eutrophication. • Promote a wide implementation of the real-time estrogenicity sensor for the monitoring of groundwater and wastewater in different contexts. • Implementation of the RAINREC modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems in aquifers characterized by different contexts. • Increase the awareness of civil society groups on the issues of water scarcity and groundwater protection.

MAR2PROTECT CS#5 - Cape Flats, South Africa	
<p>Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU legislation not applicable as this case study is located in Africa. <p>South African legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Water Act 36 of 1998, sections s21(b) and s21(e). • National Environmental Management Act 107 of 1998. • National Water Services Act 107 of 1997.
<p>Policy implications</p>	<p>The development of an estrogenicity biosensor can represent a driver for the development of policies highlighting the need for effect-based testing of water intended for Managed Aquifer Recharge, as such testing can serve as a proxy for bio-active chemicals such as pharmaceuticals and personal care products potentially present in the waters used for MAR.</p>
<p>Market implications</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market placement of the FERT-ROOT technology to reduce fertilizer leaching into aquifers. • Market placement of the real-time estrogenicity sensor. • Market placement of the RAINREC modelling tool for the design of managed aquifer recharge systems.

3.1.6. MAR2PROTECT Case Study 6 - Marbella, Spain

MAR2PROTECT CS#6 - Marbella, Spain	
	Managed aquifer recharge of a coastal aquifer affected by salt intrusion, using GW from an upstream carbonate aquifer.
Location	Marbella, Spain
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 3.1.6.2 Hydrogeological map of the Marbella-Estepona aquifer Source of hydrogeological map: Argamasilla, 2017.</i></p>
Keywords	Salinity intrusion, managed aquifer recharge, coastal aquifer, AI-based decision support system (DSS).
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	As a result of climate change and population growth, groundwater levels are declining and water quality is deteriorating due to seawater intrusion.

MAR2PROTECT CS#6 - Marbella, Spain	
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The M-AI-R-DSS and REACH tools are at an advanced stage of development. The case study LivingLab was launched and civil society engagement activities have been designed.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Señorío is a pliocene 5 km² coastal aquifer strongly affected by subsidence and salinity intrusion, during drought events with EC peaks of 3000 µS/cm. To curb salt intrusion and increase the 0.9 hm³/yr natural recharge rate, water utility HYDRALIA implemented a 0.2 hm³/yr MAR scheme, drawing water from an upstream 24 km² carbonate aquifer of high quality (EC 300 µS/cm). The following challenges need to be tackled: i) as GW abstraction from the Señorío aquifer is at 100% of natural recharge rate + existing MAR, considering the predicted increase in GW abstraction due to population growth and in sea level due to climate change, the MAR rate needs to be increased by including further water sources characterised by low salinity; ii) as the water level in the upstream aquifers shows high fluctuations with no water availability during drought periods, a control system of the MAR based on real-time monitoring of upstream GW level and downstream salinity is needed; iii) the MAR project needs to be integrated to Earth observation techniques to monitor its effectiveness in curbing subsidence.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development and calibration to the Señorío aquifer of: i) the M-AI-R-DSS tool, for the design of MAR systems, the cost analysis and the optimisation of MAR operation; and ii) the REACH tool for the assessment of the impact of economic growth and climate change on groundwater quality and quantity. Development and implementation of an innovative methodology to establish LivingLabs across MAR2PROTECT case studies. Organisation of LivingLab activities addressed to engage stakeholders, establish LivingLab teams and co-design broader societal engagement interventions across the MAR2PROTECT case studies.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>Cetaqua, the leader of this case study, is developing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> An innovative AI-based DSS, named M-AI-R-DSS, for the design of MAR systems, the cost analysis and the optimization of MAR operation (activation of periodic maintenance, optimization of flow rate to increase recharge efficiency, control of clogging). The REACH tool for the assessment of the impact of economic growth and climate change on groundwater quality and quantity, taking into account different climate change scenarios. <p>Replication potential:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The type of MAR implemented in this case study has a high replication potential, given the high number of cases in which MAR using water from upstream aquifers represents a suitable solution for aquifer protection. Moreover, a backup MAR has been identified (Aloha MAR system) to enhance the replication potential.

MAR2PROTECT CS#6 - Marbella, Spain	
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M-AI-R-DSS tool, for the design of MAR systems, the cost analysis and the optimisation of MAR operation, calibrated and implemented in at least 4 MAR2PROTECT case studies. • REACH tool for the assessment of the impact of economic growth and climate change on groundwater quality and quantity, calibrated and implemented in at least 4 MAR2PROTECT case studies.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-based DSS (M-AI-R DSS tool) (current TRL 3/expected TRL 5). • REACH tool (current TRL 3/expected TRL 5).
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development, calibration and implementation in at least 4 MAR2PROTECT case studies of the M-AI-R-DSS tool, for the design of MAR systems, the cost analysis and the optimization of MAR operation, and the REACH tool for the assessment of the impact of economic growth and climate change on groundwater quality and quantity. • Assessment of the proposed tools, enhancement of their replication potential and implementation of civil society engagement activities, through the involvement of a large stakeholder community by means of a LivingLab based on this case study. <p>Beyond the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the replication of the M-AI-R-DSS and REACH tools. • Increase the awareness of civil society groups on the issues of water scarcity and groundwater protection.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC: Establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater. • Groundwater Directive 2006/118/EC: Establishes specific measures as provided for in Article 17(1) and (2) of Directive 2000/60/EC in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution. <p>Andalusian and Spanish legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • River Basin Water Plan (Andalusian Mediterranean Basins) Third cycle (2022 - 2027). • Andalusian Water Law (2010). • Royal Decree-law for the approval of the Regional Action Climate Plan (2021). • Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plan (2018). • National Royal Decree-law for water reclamation (RD 1620/2007).
Policy implications	<p>M-AI-R-DSS can guide policy briefs to propose monitoring approaches for several types of risks involved in the design, and O&M phases of a MAR system (e.g., clogging, human health risk). The proposed monitoring approaches will be aimed at enhancing the social acceptance of MAR schemes, especially those fed with treated wastewater.</p>

MAR2PROTECT CS#6 - Marbella, Spain

Market implications

Market placement of the M-AI-R-DSS tool, for the design of MAR systems, the cost analysis and the optimisation of MAR operation.

Market placement of the REACH tool for the assessment of the impact of economic growth and climate change on groundwater quality and quantity.

3.1.7. MAR2PROTECT Case Study 7 - Lima River Estuary, Portugal

MAR2PROTECT CS#7 - Lima River Estuary, Portugal

Protection of coastal aquifer and decrease of salinity intrusion by microbial-assisted re-vegetation-based phytoremediation of estuary sediments and surface water

Location

Lima River Estuary, Portugal

Pictures illustrating the case studies

Figure 3.1.7.1. Demosite 6. MAR2PROTECT Location Map (FEUGA 2022)

MAR2PROTECT CS#7 - Lima River Estuary, Portugal

Figure 3.1.7.2. Lima river estuary © Marisa Almeida)

Keywords

Surface water, nature-based solutions, salinity intrusion, estuary, wetlands, ecosystem services, phytoremediation, micropollutants.

Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges

As a result of climate change and population growth, the contamination of sediments and surface water in the estuary is increasing, as well as salinity intrusion from the sea.

Current status of the case study:

- The revegetation/phytoremediation approach is being tested at a lab scale.
- The ecosystem model is under development.

Key intervention and objectives

The Lima River Estuary, the end member of an international watershed in NW Portugal, receives diffuse pollution from agriculture, untreated MWW and industrial WW. Estuary sediments and SW are contaminated by nutrients, metals, EDCs and pharmaceuticals, and PAHs (all 16 considered a priority by EPA), which can generate a risk if transported to the aquifer. During tides, salt intrusion extends up to 20 km upstream in the river, strongly limiting the possibility of using river water for irrigation or drinking water production. Extreme weather events periodically cause relevant erosion.

- Development of a phytoremediation approach, based on re-vegetation of specific portions of the estuary, to promote uptake and/or biodegradation of contaminants in sediment and surface water.
- Development and validation of an ecosystem services model to quantify the effectiveness of estuary revegetation in reducing salt intrusion upstream in the river associated with sea tides and coastal erosion due to extreme weather events, considering different climate change scenarios.
- Development and implementation of an innovative methodology to establish LivingLabs across MAR2PROTECT case studies.
- Organisation of LivingLab activities addressed to engage stakeholders, establish LivingLab teams and co-design broader societal engagement interventions in this case study.

MAR2PROTECT CS#7 - Lima River Estuary, Portugal	
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>CIIMAR, the leader of this case study, is developing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A phytoremediation approach, based on re-vegetation of specific portions of the estuary, to promote uptake and/or biodegradation of contaminants in sediment and surface water. • An ecosystem services model to quantify the effectiveness of estuary revegetation in reducing salt intrusion upstream in the river associated with sea tides and coastal erosion due to extreme weather events, considering different climate change scenarios. <p>Replication potential: The approach promoted in this case study for the sustainable management of estuarine wetlands has a high replication potential, given the high number of estuaries characterised by water and sediment contamination and seawater intrusion.</p>
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation at TRL 5 in a real estuary environment of a phytoremediation approach, based on re-vegetation of specific portions of the estuary, to promote uptake and biodegradation of sediment and surface water contaminants. • Development, calibration and validation in a real estuary of an ecosystem services model to quantify the effectiveness of estuary revegetation in reducing salt intrusion upstream in the river associated with sea tides and coastal erosion due to extreme sea storms.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<p>Nature-based solution through phytoremediation with salt marsh plants for micropollutants removal (current TRL 3/4, expected TRL 5).</p>
Relevant sectors	<p>Câmara Municipal de Viana do Castelo (local municipality), Capitania do Porto de Viana do Castelo (local authority), APA (National environmental agency); ARHN (Regional environmental agency); CMIA de Viana do Castelo (local org. for science dissemination to schools/general public).</p>
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation at TRL 5 in a real estuary environment of a phytoremediation approach, based on re-vegetation of specific portions of the estuary, to promote uptake and/or biodegradation of contaminants in sediment and surface water. • Development, calibration and validation in a real estuary of an ecosystem services model to quantify the effectiveness of estuary revegetation in reducing salt intrusion upstream in the river associated with sea tides and coastal erosion due to extreme weather events. <p>Beyond the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the replication of the phytoremediation/revegetation approach for the sustainable management of estuarine environments. • Increase the awareness of civil society groups on the issues of water scarcity and groundwater protection.

MAR2PROTECT CS#7 - Lima River Estuary, Portugal	
<p>Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)</p>	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC: Establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater. • Groundwater Directive 2006/118/EC: Establishes specific measures as provided for in Article 17(1) and (2) of Directive 2000/60/EC in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution. <p>Portuguese legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lei da Água n.o 58/2005 (Water Law) https://files.dre.pt/1s/2005/12/249a00/72807310.pdf.
<p>Policy implications</p>	<p>The ecosystem service model and the wetland phytoremediation approach developed in this case study can help to formulate policy recommendations aimed at promoting guidelines and legislation aimed at a stringer protection of estuarine environments and at increasing their tourist value.</p>
<p>Market implications</p>	<p>Not expected</p>

3.2. NINFA case studies

NINFA includes 8 case studies which are included in the presentation below:

- Case study 1 - Achterhoek, Gelderland, Netherlands
- Case study 2 - Los Alcazares, Murcia, Spain
- Case study 3 - Terrassa, Catalonia, Spain
- Case study 4 - Butry-sur-Oise, Île-de-France, France
- Case study 5 - Ibiza, Balear Islands, Spain
- Case study 6 - Colombia
- Case study 7 - Mexico
- Case study 8 - Egypt

3.2.1. NINFA Case Study 1 – Achterhoek, Netherlands

NINFA CS#1 – Achterhoek, Netherlands	
	Achterhoek
Location	Gelderland, Netherlands
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 3.2.1. Map of the Achterhoek area in the Gelderland province. Points correspond to drinking water production wells. Models are centred in the Klooster area, in the Baakse Beek sub-basin (© Sathish Sadhasivam 2025)</i></p>
Keywords	Groundwater, CEC, modelling, monitoring technologies, groundwater depletion, drought, transport model, organic micro-pollutants
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	Regarding GW quality, droughts have been increasingly common in this area in recent years, and it is projected that they will become more severe and frequent in the future as a result of climate change. The summer of 2018 was an extreme example of drought in the Netherlands, with high temperatures and below-average precipitation causing a significant precipitation deficit.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study area has recently experienced drought conditions, resulting in a notable decline in the groundwater table. • This reduction in groundwater levels has had consequential impacts on agricultural and economic activities within the region. • In response, the Dutch government has undertaken initiatives to render the area more resilient to climate-related challenges. • However, there exists a knowledge gap regarding the potential effects of these governmental measures on groundwater quality.

NINFA CS#1 – Achterhoek, Netherlands	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing this concern, the NINFA project endeavors to develop sophisticated transport models and scenarios aimed at effectively managing the groundwater system. • Presently, the flow model has reached its finalization stage, with plans for subsequent expansion to incorporate transport models pertaining to nitrate and select organic micropollutants.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>The Rhine IJssel Water Board has been working on the development of this area to create a robust and future-proof water system in the Baakse Beek estate zone. Although this area is part of the Gelders Natuurnetwerk (GNN) and its nature is protected, it has been drying up, which means that the current groundwater situation is not optimal due to human influence. Measures are being sought to create a climate-proof, robust water system in which the various functions, including agriculture, are strengthened and a better situation is created for the landscape and heritage.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a cost-efficient monitoring strategy based on the integration of existing sensors and analytical approaches with innovative tools. • Assess the existing sources and pathways of GW pollution, their synergistic effects with stressors such as droughts and floods or prevention/mitigation measures, by testing and validating hydrogeological and reactive transport models for nutrients, pesticides, and emerging contaminants from wastewater. Furthermore, it is proposed to create management scenarios and propose measures to mitigate the effects of drought on the groundwater system.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The NINFA project will research how drought and drought-relief measures affect groundwater quality, with a focus on nitrate and organic micropollutants. • Implementing AI-based hydrological and transport models can help utilities predict and mitigate the impacts of drought on water supply and quality, enhancing their resilience against climate change. • The assessment of sources and pathways of groundwater pollution can guide utilities in implementing targeted measures to reduce contaminants, particularly nitrate and organic micropollutants. • The development of regional management scenarios based on the project's findings can help regions tailor their groundwater management approaches to local conditions, enhancing climate resilience. • The project's focus on nitrate and organic micropollutants can inform further research into emerging contaminants. • By adopting climate-proof water management strategies, regions and utilities can better withstand the effects of climate change, ensuring the sustainability of water resources. • The replication of successful measures can lead to significant improvements in groundwater quality, reducing health risks and ensuring safe drinking water supplies.

NINFA CS#1 – Achterhoek, Netherlands	
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop Hydrological and transport models using convectional AI model techniques. • Develop (at least 6) scenarios to manage the groundwater system during the drought periods considering the groundwater quality.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative monitoring strategies (current TRL3/ expected TRL 5) • Hydrogeological and reactive transport models (current TRL4/ expected TRL 5) • Risk assessment (current TRL3/ expected TRL 5) • NINFA Platform (current TRL3/ expected TRL 5)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and validation of AI-enhanced hydrological and reactive transport models. • Accurate prediction and management of groundwater resources, addressing the impacts of drought and pollution effectively. • Creation of actionable management scenarios tailored to mitigate the effects of drought on groundwater systems. <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the replication of the project's successful methodologies and technologies in other regions facing similar groundwater and climate challenges. • Develop adaptive management strategies that evolve with changing climate conditions and technological advancements. • Contribute to the creation of standardised guidelines for sustainable groundwater management. • Contribute to the creation of standardised guidelines for sustainable groundwater management.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC: Establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater. • Groundwater Directive 2006/118/EC: Establishes specific measures as provided for in Article 17(1) and (2) of Directive 2000/60/EC in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution <p>Netherlands legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Management Act (Wet Milieubeheer): Provides a comprehensive framework for environmental protection, including water and soil quality.
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Potential) Effective mitigation strategies can reduce the adverse impacts of drought and pollution on groundwater resources. • (Potential) Create frameworks for implementing drought and pollution mitigation measures, such as artificial recharge and optimised irrigation

NINFA CS#1 – Achterhoek, Netherlands

Market implications Advanced software tools that use AI to predict groundwater behavior and pollutant transport under various scenarios.

3.2.2. NINFA Case Study 2 - Los Alcázares, Spain

NINFA CS#2- Los Alcázares, Spain

Los Alcázares

Location

Murcia, Spain

Pictures illustrating the case studies

Figure 3.2.2.1. a). location of CS3 in Spain (Geological Survey of Spain, IGME-CSIC visor). b) Whitening event due to pollutant load from GW into Mar Menor coastal lagoon (© IEO-CSIC)

Keywords

Groundwater, saline intrusion, nitrate, CEC, nature-based solutions, sensors, modelling

Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges

- Seawater intrusion, the filtration of irrigation water, which has increased since the construction of the transfer, as well as periodic intense rains, have made the water table so high that water surfaces on to the ground at some points. These upper layers of the aquifer are highly polluted with nitrates, pesticides and nutrients and drains directly to the Mar Menor which often suffers severe eutrophication episodes resulting in reduction in water transparency and several episodes of anoxia (see Figure above).

Current status of the case study

- The hydrological model for the case study is currently in development.

NINFA CS#2- Los Alcázares, Spain	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The sensory device underwent testing in the lab, and fieldwork is scheduled for summer 2025 to install and test these sensors at the case study site.
Key intervention and objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Los Alcázares is a Spanish municipality in the autonomous community of Murcia, in the southeast of Spain (see Figure above). Los Alcázares is located on the coast of Mar Menor, which is Europe's largest saltwater lagoon with almost 170 km², and an area of great ecological, geological and scenic importance. Its surrounding areas are particularly rich in landscape values, and it is an area where up to ten approved environmental protection figures converge. Robust, real-time and affordable sensors will be developed in the lab will be tested at certain sites for GW monitoring and early-detection of pollutants. Assess the existing sources and pathways of GW pollution, their synergistic effects with stressors such as droughts and floods or prevention/mitigation measures, by testing and validating hydrogeological and reactive transport models for pollutants of interest. Develop a train of treatment technologies including nature-based solutions (NBS), to minimise nutrients, pesticides and other pollutants (metals and antibiotics from manure) leaching to GWs.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>The Campo de Cartagena groundwater mass faces the threat of not meeting required quantitative and chemical standards, as highlighted by the Segura Hydrographic Confederation. This area, a crucial supplier of winter vegetables to European markets, heavily depends on irrigation, primarily sourced from the Tagus-Segura Water Transfer and groundwater. Overuse of the deeper aquifer layers is prominent, while the upper aquifer suffers from an excess of water, leading to issues such as seawater intrusion and water table elevation. Intensive agricultural practices, including fertigation and extensive manure application, contribute to contamination of the aquifer with nitrates, pesticides, and nutrients.</p> <p>Replication potential:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water utilities can replicate the cost-efficient monitoring strategies developed in this project, integrating existing sensors with innovative tools. This can improve the detection and management of groundwater quality issues. Implementing hydrological and transport models can help utilities predict and mitigate the impacts of drought on water supply and quality, enhancing their resilience against climate change.
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop robust, real-time, and affordable sensors for groundwater monitoring. Explore prevention and mitigation measures for groundwater pollution. Validate hydrogeological and reactive transport models for targeted pollutants. Design a treatment train comprising membrane-based technologies, Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP), and nature-based solutions.

NINFA CS#2- Los Alcázares, Spain	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement the treatment train to minimise leaching of nutrients, pesticides, metals, and antibiotics from manure into groundwater.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovative monitoring strategies and sensors (current TRL3/ expected TRL 5) Hydrogeological and reactive transport models (current TRL4/ expected TRL 5) Risk assessment (current TRL3/ expected TRL 5) Treatment technologies: Solid/liquid separation + membrane filtration + AOP + Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) + inoculated biochar + woodchip bioreactor and electrowetland (NBS) for minimising nutrients and pesticides leaching (current TRL3/ expected TRL 5) NINFA Platform (current TRL3/ expected TRL 5)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop advanced sensors that are able to characterise the groundwater quality aspects. Apply different trains of technologies to minimise the infiltration of nitrates and pesticides in GW. <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support continuous innovation in monitoring systems, hydrological models, technologies and management strategies.
Key legislation and policies (EU/ national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC: Establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater. Groundwater Directive 2006/118/EC: Establishes specific measures as provided for in Article 17(1) and (2) of Directive 2000/60/EC in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution. Regulation (EU) 2020/741: Lays down minimum water quality requirements for the safe reuse of treated urban wastewaters for agricultural irrigation between EU countries <p>Spanish legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Royal Decree 1085/2024: Establishes a legal framework for the reuse of treated wastewater for 5 intended reuse categories and lays down minimum water quality requirements.
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time monitoring can lead to more responsive and adaptive management strategies. Organic and circular fertilizers can be promoted in sensitive and highly impacted areas.
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development and commercialisation of advanced groundwater monitoring sensors and systems, and modular trains of technologies.

3.2.3. NINFA Case Study 3 – Terrassa, Spain

NINFA CS#3 - Terrassa, Spain	
	Terrassa
Location	Terrassa, Barcelona, Spain
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 3.2.3. Location of Terrassa in Catalonia, Spain (© ICGC)</i></p>
Keywords	Groundwater, heavy metals (HM), microplastics (MP) and hydrocarbons (HC), nature-based solutions, urban runoff, reclaimed water, train of technologies
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	Although there are no water quality wells, GW is suspected to be contaminated with urban runoff, since 43.2% of the aquifer area is urban/industrial soil.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A pilot site has been set in a parking zone to collect all runoff water from the area and measure HC, MP and HM. • Contacts with the Municipality of Terrassa has been made to study any potential location of a new urban pilot.
Key intervention and objectives	Terrassa is a city located in the comarca del Vallès Occidental with an extension of about 70.2 km ² and which belongs to the province of Barcelona, one of the four provinces that are part of Catalonia, Spain. Terrassa originated as a Roman city of Egara in the 1st century, during the reign of the Roman emperor Vespasian. It was founded close to the Vallparadís torrent, which originates in Matadepera and passes through Terrassa.

NINFA CS#3 - Terrassa, Spain	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and select a pilot site in Terrassa for addressing groundwater contamination caused by urban runoff. • Develop and test an optimised train of technologies to produce reclaimed water from urban runoff, focusing on biological (Nature-based solutions, NBS), chemical (Advanced Oxidation Processes, AOPs), and physical processes (membranes). • Evaluate the effectiveness of using reclaimed water for various purposes such as irrigation, street cleaning, and indirect aquifer recharge. • Implement the train of technologies to remove hydrocarbons (HCs) and microplastics (MPs) from urban runoff. • Incorporate processes for the recovery of selected metals (Platinum (Pt) and Palladium (Pd)) originating from car catalysts and brakes into the treatment train. • Monitor the performance and efficiency of the treatment train in removing contaminants and recovering metals.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terrassa is located in an area with good permeable and porous materials that conform the aquifer and would allow the passage of rainwater. However, a big part of its central area is an urban area, all paved with concrete and asphalt, which difficult drainage and leads to severe floods in the center of the city after storm events. The surroundings of the city center suffer a strong industrial activity which may increase the vulnerability of the aquifer due to the high pollution and the high rate of permeability. <p>Replication potential: Treatment train with specific low-cost unit operations that can be implemented in other urban areas.</p>
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and test an optimised train of technologies to produce reclaimed water from urban runoff, focusing on biological (Nature-based solutions, NBS), chemical (Advanced Oxidation Processes, AOPs), and physical processes (membranes).
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treatment technologies: Metal recovery (Pd, Pt) through membrane concentration + chemical extraction + centrifugal and/or electromagnetic separation / Modular Green tile (NBS) + ad hoc AOPs for hydrocarbons and MP removal (Current TRL3 / Expected TRL5) • NINFA Platform (Current TRL3 / Expected TRL5)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and test an optimised train of technologies to produce reclaimed water from urban runoff. <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote local water reuse with quality to either recharge aquifers or for direct use (irrigation, urban uses, etc) by implementation of the proposed treatment technology train.

NINFA CS#3 - Terassa, Spain	
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC: Establishes a framework for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater. • Groundwater Directive 2006/118/EC: Establishes specific measures as provided for in Article 17(1) and (2) of Directive 2000/60/EC in order to prevent and control groundwater pollution. • Regulation (EU) 2020/741: Lays down minimum water quality requirements for the safe reuse of treated urban wastewaters for agricultural irrigation between EU countries <p>Spanish legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Royal Decree 1085/2024: Establishes a legal framework for the reuse of treated wastewater for 5 intended reuse categories and lays down minimum water quality requirements.
Policy implications	Foster the implementation of Sustainable Drainage Systems (SUDS) and other treatment devices to effectively eliminate hydrocarbon (HC), microplastic (MP) and heavy metal (HM) infiltration to the GW in the urban planification.
Market implications	Development and commercialisation of urban advanced modular trains of technologies.

3.2.4. NINFA Case Study 4 - Butry-sur-Oise WWTP, France

NINFA CS#4 - Butry-sur-Oise WWTP, France	
	Butry-sur-Oise WWTP
Location	Butry-sur-Oise, Île-de-France, France
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 3.2.4. Photo of WWTP at Butry-sur-Oise (© Nesles la Vallée 2024)</i></p>
Keywords	Wastewater, treatment technologies, water treatment trains, CEC, ARG, reclaimed water
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change effects such as extended periods of droughts limit the amount of water that is available for irrigation and/or recharge groundwater by infiltration. • CECs present in WWTP effluents can potentially pollute soil and/or groundwater.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently wastewater undergoes only secondary treatment with activated sludge at the WWTP. The WWTP does not have a specific tertiary treatment for the elimination of CECs.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>The wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) at Butry-sur-Oise treats on average 1163m³/day of wastewater which corresponds to a nominal capacity of 6700 population equivalent (PE). The WWTP has a secondary treatment stage where primary effluent is treated using an extended aeration activated sludge system. The treated water is then released into the Oise River which is in the Seine-Normandy watershed. The WWTP does not have a specific tertiary treatment for the elimination of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) like pharmaceuticals, microplastics (MPs) and antibiotic resistant bacteria/antibiotic resistant genes (ARBs/ARGs), which can lead to their presence in the effluent, along with certain nutrients like nitrates and phosphates. Due to the possible connection of the watershed to aquifer, the GW might present contamination with these pollutants.</p>

NINFA CS#4 - Butry-sur-Oise WWTP, France	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Characterise the main composition of CECs (pharmaceuticals, MPs and ARB/ARGs) in the WWTP effluent. • Application of a combination of low-cost Advanced Oxidation Processes, activated carbon, and biofiltration for the removal of the contaminants characterised.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigate the tertiary treatment of treated wastewater for possible reuse by indirect aquifer recharge (or other uses based on the quality). • Evaluate the performance of a combination of technologies for the removal of CECs. <p>Replication potential:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treatment train with specific low-cost unit operations that can be implemented in other WWTPs.
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elimination of CECs (pharmaceuticals, MPs and ARB/ARGs) • Obtain reclaimed water with requested quality standards that can be used to recharge aquifers indirectly or other uses based on the quality.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treatment technologies: Combined Advanced Oxidation Process+ Activated Carbon adsorption + Sand (bio) filtration for the removal of CEC and MP from WWTPs effluents (Current TRL3 / Expected TRL5) • NINFA Platform (Current TRL3 / Expected TRL5)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setup and validate pilot units of tertiary wastewater treatment technology train at WWTP at Butry-sur-oise <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote local water reuse with quality to either recharge aquifers or for direct use (irrigation, urban uses, etc.) by implementation of the proposed treatment technology train.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for wastewater reuse <p>French legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decree 2023/835 of August 29, 2023 codifying provisions on the use and conditions of use of rainwater and treated wastewater (French). • Order of December 14, 2023 on conditions for production and use of treated wastewater for watering green spaces (French). • Order of December 18, 2023 concerning the conditions of production and use of treated wastewater for crop irrigation (French).

NINFA CS#4 - Butry-sur-Oise WWTP, France	
Policy implications	Current water policies are being recast to consider the presence and elimination of CECs, the proposed treatment technologies will help to achieve the quality standards regarding CECs and in a wider perspective, water reuse in the context of water stress.
Market implications	Treatment train with specific low-cost unit operations that can be implemented in other WWTPs.

3.2.5. NINFA Case Study 5 – Ibiza, Spain

NINFA CS#5 - – Ibiza, Spain	
	Ibiza
Location	Ibiza, Balear Islands, Spain
Keywords	Replication site, groundwater, saline intrusion
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	Ibiza faces a critical water supply challenge, prompting the installation of desalination plants as part of the solution
Current status of the case study:	During RP2 data will be gathered and NINFA DSS will be adjusted.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Drinking Water Treatment Plant (DWTP) in Ibiza, situated in a Mediterranean climate, serves a landmass of 572 km² and a resident population of 147,914 individuals. However, with 2,000 tourists per every 100 residents, the island contends with significant socio-environmental pressures.</p> <p>The monitoring data collected will contribute to the creation of the Groundwater Knowledge Observatory as part of the NINFA project. Additionally, it will aid in validating the NINFA Platform, ensuring its accuracy and effectiveness.</p>
Scale & treatment, replicability	Notably, the overexploitation of groundwater resources stands out as a major concern. The island's proximity to the sea and limited natural replenishment contribute to severe issues of saline intrusion.

3.2.6. NINFA Case Study 6 – Colombia

NINFA CS#6 - Colombia	
	Colombia
Location	Colombia
Keywords	Replication site, groundwater, wastewater, drinking water treatment plant, CEC, ARG
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Bogotá River faces contamination from various sources, including Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs), Antibiotic Resistance Genes (ARGs), and Microplastics (MPs). • Both the Tachira River and the aquifer are polluted with nitrates and wastewater treatment plant effluents. The absence of a complete purification system results in insufficient drinking water quality. Efforts are underway to address these challenges and improve water safety.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During RP2 data will be gathered and NINFA DSS will be adjusted.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Two sites have been engaged:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • El Salitre Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) in Bogota: Serving a population of 7.7 million, this facility operates in a temperate climate due to its high altitude (2540-4650 m). Located in the Sabana de Bogota aquifer region, it caters to 3 million people and has recently been expanded to enhance water quality in the Bogota River. • Drinking Water Treatment Plant (DWTP) in Villa del Rosario: Serving 88,433 residents, this plant operates in a tropical-dry climate. It draws water from the Tachira-Cretaceous aquifer, which is shared with Venezuela. • The monitoring data collected will contribute to the creation of the Groundwater Knowledge Observatory as part of the NINFA project. Additionally, it will aid in validating the NINFA Platform, ensuring its accuracy and effectiveness.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In line with SDG6, the National Government established a Plan for achieving drinking water access to 8,573,951 people in 2022 (100% population in 2030) and increasing the percentage of treated wastewater up to 54.3% in 2022.

3.2.7. NINFA Case Study 7 – Mexico

NINFA CS#7 - Mexico	
	Mexico
Location	Mexico
Keywords	Replication site, groundwater, wastewater, CEC, ARG
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cuernavaca WWTP generates effluents contaminated with CEC, ARGs, MP; • San Javier DWTP in Querétaro: the aquifer is overexploited with presence of nitrates due to agriculture activity; 4 of 6 wells also present contamination with fluorides.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During RP2 data will be gathered and NINFA DSS will be adjusted.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Two key sites are targeted for intervention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cuernavaca WWTP (341,029 inhabitants; Dry-winter subtropical highland climate; Cuernavaca aquifer) • San Javier DWTP in Querétaro (794,789 inhabitants; Cold semiarid -steppe- climate; Queretaro aquifer): the aquifer is overexploited (average availability of -63.7 hm³/year) • The monitoring data collected will contribute to the creation of the Groundwater Knowledge Observatory as part of the NINFA project. Additionally, it will aid in validating the NINFA Platform, ensuring its accuracy and effectiveness.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In Mexico, significant challenges persist regarding wastewater treatment and access to drinking water, with only 37.8% of wastewater treated and 10.5 million lacking sewage access, alongside 9 million without drinking water access. Moreover, 157 out of 653 aquifers were overexploited in 2019, with 50 becoming overexploited in the last two years.

3.2.8. NINFA Case Study 8 - Egypt

NINFA CS#8 - Egypt	
	Egypt
Location	Egypt
Keywords	Replication site, groundwater
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Egypt faces a critical water scarcity challenge, nearing 'absolute water scarcity' levels defined by the UN. • Contaminants in the WWTP effluent include nutrients, Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs), Antibiotic Resistance Genes (ARGs), and Microplastics (MP).
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During RP2 data will be gathered and NINFA DSS will be adjusted.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>The Nile Delta aquifer, vital for groundwater supply, including the Abu Rawash Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP), is under pressure. Despite Nile replenishment, the aquifer is impacted by direct exposure to the Mediterranean Sea and Suez Canal. Groundwater availability has annually declined since 1981, while pollution from agriculture, population density, and wastewater effluents, notably from the Abu Rawash WWTP, degrade water quality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The monitoring data collected will contribute to the creation of the Groundwater Knowledge Observatory as part of the NINFA project. Additionally, it will aid in validating the NINFA Platform, ensuring its accuracy and effectiveness.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although the aquifer is replenished directly by the Nile water, it is also in direct contact with the Mediterranean Sea (north) and the Suez Canal (east). Since 1981 the GW potentiality is decreasing annually in a linear fashion by 0.1 billion m³.

3.3. UPWATER case studies

UPWATER includes 3 case studies which are included in the presentation below:

- Case study 1 - Stengaarden dumpsite in Denmark
- Case study 2 - Athens metropolitan region in Greece
- Case study 3 - Barcelona metropolitan region in Spain

3.3.1. UPWATER Case Study 1 - Stengaarden dumpsite, Denmark

UPWATER CS#1 - Stengaarden dumpsite, Denmark	
	Stengaarden dumpsite in Denmark
Location	Aquifer beneath Stengaarden dump site, Region Sjælland, DK
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p>Figure 3.3.1.1. Picture of Stengaarden dumpsite. The dumpsite is now covered with soil (Brown field front–right) (reprinted with permission from Region of Sjaelland, Denmark).</p>

UPWATER CS#1 - Stengaarden dumpsite, Denmark

Figure 3.3.1.2. The Stengaarden pilot in autumn 2023. From left to right: 1) white tank: Inlet buffer tank; 2) black cylinders (1 front and one hind): [Moving Bed Biofilm Reactors \(MBBR\)](#), 3) white tanks: buffer tanks as inlet for the biofilters; 4) steel tanks (outside the container): biofilters (© Dr. Andrea Mongelli, 2023).

Keywords	Groundwater, nature-based solutions, dumpsite, CEC, pesticides, rural area, temperate climate
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More intensive rainfalls and related transfer of pollutants into the groundwater. • Prolonged periods of drought and related increases in contaminant concentrations.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MBBR pilot correctly installed and over a year of experiments conducted and continuous monitoring ongoing. • 1st monitoring campaign on groundwater completed.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Polluted rural area at which the groundwater is impacted by pesticide wastes; pollutants to be studied: phenoxy acid pesticides, iron; monitoring systems: direct sampling plus direct HPLC-MS/MS in comparison to ceramic passive samplers for organic contaminant monitoring, diffusive gradients in thin films for trace metal monitoring, source apportionment-modelling; mitigation solution: Moving Bed Biofilm Reactors (MBBR) and biofilters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MBBR and biofilters will be used to remove pesticide contamination. The aim is to achieve drinking water quality. • Elaboration of effective preventive measures to diffuse pollution in participatory processes with stakeholders to produce policy recommendations.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MBBR and biofilters will be used to remove pesticide contamination from groundwater – both technologies will at the large work as biofilm systems, with the biofilters being expected to also be able to

UPWATER CS#1 - Stengaarden dumpsite, Denmark	
	<p>utilise phytoremediation. The MBBR will be tested for bio-Fenton capacities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two parallel trains with a capacity of about 30 L/h. Testing for capacity will be a major part of UPWATER. The size is about 1/1000 of full-scale • It is expected the solution will work as managed aquifer recharge (MAR) <p>In Northern Europe temperatures below zero are expected in winter. Thus, the demonstration on operationality of the solution for minus temperatures is crucial to ensure replicability.</p>
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is expected to be demonstrated whether a biofilter can in principle be operated all year round under Danish weather conditions. • It is expected to demonstrate whether the approach is resilient to the high iron load or can even utilise it. • Developed biobased solutions will be able to prevent and mitigate GW pollution to concentration levels below toxicity and water quality guideline thresholds, but at least a 90% reduction is expected for chemicals to reach drinking water quality to defuse the situation for a well field for producing drinking water nearby. • Policy briefs at national level - to provide evidence of harmful pollutants affecting GW with case-specific recommendations.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passive sampling as monitoring technology for CEC and trace metal contamination. • Nature-based solutions (MBBR plus biofilters) to treat GW pollution.
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate NBS in environmental conditions to mitigate ground water pollution with pesticides, moving from TRL 3 to 5. • Develop compound specific isotope analysis for pesticides and in combination with ceramic passive samplers. <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of novel NBS solutions which will enable the operator to i) protect GW pollution and ii) save developing and applying energy intensive chemical treatment and thus save CO₂ emission equivalents for 35 Wh/m³ • Implementation of integrated passive sampling instead of traditional grab water sampling which will imply an overall cost reduction for the GW directive of 2Meur/year in GW routine monitoring (market size = 15.930). • Implementation of integrated passive sampling instead of traditional grab water sampling which will imply an overall cost reduction for the WFD directive of 60Meur/year in WFD routine monitoring (market size = 146.510). • Influence relevant local/regional and EU policy updates.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU drinking water directive (DWD), EU groundwater directive (GWD)

UPWATER CS#1 - Stengaarden dumpsite, Denmark	
	<p>Danish legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pesticide taxation scheme, • Missing legislation on diffuse groundwater pollution in Denmark
Policy implications	<p>Independently from the concrete case Stengaarden, in Denmark there are missing policies on protecting groundwater against diffuse pollution such as groundwater protection zones. UPWATER will discuss groundwater protection zones as preventive measures to groundwater contamination a) by law and b) by mutual agreements (PPPs) with the Danish authorities and utilities.</p> <p>Findings from this case study may be incorporated into recommendations for improvements in existing and proposed EU policies, including Water Framework Directive, Groundwater Directive, Drinking Water Directive, and the proposed Water Resilience Initiative, if it proceeds.</p>
Market implications	<p>MBBRs have proven quite successful for treating wastewater. It is the first time these are used for treating contaminated groundwater. There are two companies that would be interested in approaching this market.</p> <p>Biofiltration is getting more and more popular (both rapid and slow filtration), though it is difficult to transfer knowledge from one case to another.</p>

3.3.2. UPWATER Case Study 2 - Athens metropolitan region, Greece

UPWATER CS#2 - Athens metropolitan region, Greece	
	Athens metropolitan region in Greece
Location	River Kifisos, Athens, Greece
Pictures illustrating the case studies	
	<p>Figure 3.3.2.1. Map over the River Kifisos catchment, Athens, Greece (© Prof. Andreas Kallioras, 2023).</p> <p>Figure 3.3.2.2: (i) Installations of monitoring stations in the Kifisos River, (ii) the shallow infiltration well system and (iii) construction of floating root mats and a bioelectrochemical wetland based on biochar for NBS pilot experiments at the Athens Municipality Nursery (© Prof. Andreas Kallioras, 2023).</p>

UPWATER CS#2 - Athens metropolitan region, Greece	
Keywords	Groundwater, surface water, urban area, nutrients, CECs, PFAS, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), trace metals, pathogens, nature-based solutions, shallow-infiltration wells, constructed wetlands, hydroinformatics, Mediterranean climate.
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water scarcity and prolonged drought periods and related increases in contaminant concentrations • Flash flood phenomena in urban and peri-urban environment • Wild-fires in the mountainous zone of the catchment
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wetland/shallow-well pilot in the process of construction • 1st monitoring campaign with passive samplers completed • 2nd monitoring campaign on-going
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Polluted urban area; pollutants to be studied: nutrients, metals, CEC, PFAS, PAH and viruses; Monitoring systems: <u>ceramic passive samplers for organic contaminant monitoring</u>, virus passive samplers, diffusive gradients in thin films for monitoring of bioavailable trace metals; Mitigation solutions: bioelectrochemical wetland, shallow-infiltration well.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioelectrochemical wetlands will be used to remove contamination with nutrients, trace metals, and CEC. The aim is to achieve improvement of treated wastewater effluent, ideally up to drinking water quality, for minimisation of environmental impacts to the underlying aquifer and the marine environment. • Shallow-infiltration wells will be used to remove contamination with nutrients, trace metals, and CEC. The aim is to achieve improvement of infiltrating water in the hyporheic zone for MAR applications in urban environments. • Elaboration of effective site-specific preventive measures in participatory processes with stakeholders to produce policy recommendations.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel wetland technology will be used to remove contamination with nutrients, trace metals, and CECs. • 3 cells of 6 m² each treating a maximum water flow of 10 m³/d • Shallow-infiltration well for in-situ remediation of river water quality (cylindrical device of 1x0.5m) <p>Replication potential:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The shallow-infiltration wells are envisaged to be replicated in rectangular shape constructions transversely along Kifisos river course for the improvement of infiltrating water quality within the hyporheic zone. • The shallow-infiltration wells can be replicated in similar urban environments as point Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) solutions for urban settings using stormwater as recharge source. • Wetland systems may be replicated in similar urban environments • Wetland systems may be upscaled and implemented in riverbed settings close to wastewater discharge zones, for large-scale treatment of wastewater treatment plant effluent.

UPWATER CS#2 - Athens metropolitan region, Greece	
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy briefs at local/regional level - to provide evidence of harmful pollutants affecting GW with case-specific recommendations. • Developed biobased solutions will be able to prevent and mitigate GW pollution to concentration levels below toxicity and water quality guideline thresholds, but at least an 90% reduction is expected for chemicals and 2-3 log units for pathogens (absolute values). • Contribute to the re-design of the monitoring network of the regional water authority based on UPWATER results.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passive sampling as monitoring technology for CEC, trace metal and virus contamination • Nature-based solutions (bioelectrochemical wetlands and shallow infiltration wells) to treat GW pollution • Low-energy and low-cost Long Range (LoRa) sensors with zero-cost data transfer requirements for monitoring of water level, chemical oxygen demand (COD) equivalent, total suspended solids (TSS) equivalent, temperature, NH₄-N, automatic water-sampler system, as well as soil moisture, pH, & temperature in the unsaturated zone
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimise passive sampler technology and validate for groundwater conditions, moving from TRL 3-4, depending on sampler type, to TRL 5-6. • Validate novel NBS technology in environmental conditions to mitigate surface water pollution and protect groundwater, moving from TRL 3 to 5 • Development of an integrated monitoring scheme for real-time hydrologic data acquisition on the catchment scale • Integration of the UPWATER monitoring stations with the national research infrastructure for river gauging in Greece • Development of an urban hydro-environmental observatory for the Kifisos catchment in Athens <p>Beyond the project :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of novel NBS solutions which will enable the operator to i) protect GW pollution and ii) save developing and applying energy intensive chemical treatment and thus save CO₂ emission equivalents for 35 Wh/m³ • Influence relevant local/regional and EU policy updates • Support of the UPWATER data platform (UPWATER CLOUD) to the Greek national research infrastructure for river gauging • Replicate the shallow-wells in rectangular-shaped units along the river-source to improve the quality of infiltrating water in the hyporheic zone. • Implementation of integrated passive sampling instead of traditional grab water sampling which will imply an overall cost reduction for the GW directive of 1-2 M€/year in GW routine monitoring (EU market size = 15.930) • Implementation of integrated passive sampling instead of traditional grab water sampling which will imply an overall cost reduction for the WFD directive of 26-60 M€/year in WFD routine monitoring (EU market size = 146.510). <p>The calculations behind these cost savings assume a cost reduction of 15–35 EUR/sample, depending on whether isotopes are included in the analysis or not, four monitoring campaigns/year in GW sampling and 12 monitoring</p>

UPWATER CS#2 - Athens metropolitan region, Greece	
	campaigns/year in surface water sampling, and 15.930 and 146.510 sampling points for GW and surface water, respectively (Hypothesis over WISE database sources for GW and WFD reporting).
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>EU legislation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC). • The Groundwater Directive (2006/118/EC). • The Drinking Water Directive (EU) 2020/2184. • The Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (91/271/EEC). • Environmental Quality Standards Directive (2008/105/EC) • Industrial Emissions Directive (2010/75/EU). • REACH Regulation (1907/2006). • Water Reuse Regulation (EU) 2020/741. • Floods Directive (2007/60/EC). <p>Greek legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint Ministerial Decree 145116/2011: Definition of measures, conditions, and procedure for wastewater reuse • Presidential Decree 51/2007 • Law 3199/03 on water protection and the sustainable management of the water resources • Regional Water Directories and Councils • River Basin Management Plan – Attica River Basin District (GR06)
Policy implications	<p>Findings may be relevant to updating local policies for implementing integral water cycle management, control mechanisms of contamination risks at source and before reaching natural aquatic systems and using NBS to treat wastewater and reduce marine environment pollution. As water reuse and stormwater management can increase resilience in a changing climate and water demand, policies also aim to increase the use of alternative water resources, such as NBS-treated wastewater. The elaboration of effective site-specific preventive measures can further contribute to policy improvement.</p> <p>Findings from this case study may be incorporated into recommendations for improvements in existing and proposed EU policies, including Water Framework Directive, Groundwater Directive, Drinking Water Directive, and the proposed Water Resilience Initiative, if it proceeds.</p>
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The applied Long Range (LoRa) technologies can be adopted by water utilities for monitoring of water-related parameters in wastewater treatment plants at several steps of wastewater treatment processes using low-energy sensors of low-cost systems with zero-cost data transfer requirements. • Where passive sampling can replace traditional grab sampling, significant savings can be made (see section ‘Ambition at the end of the project and beyond’)

3.3.3. UPWATER Case Study 3 - Besòs Barcelona metropolitan region, Spain

UPWATER CS#3 - Barcelona metropolitan region, Spain	
	Barcelona metropolitan region in Spain
Location	Besòs river and aquifer, Barcelona, Spain
Pictures illustrating the case studies	

UPWATER CS#3 - Barcelona metropolitan region, Spain

JUNE 2023

JULY 2023

Figure 3.2.3.2. Nature-Based Solutions installed at the outlet of the waste water treatment plant EDAR Montcada I Reixac in Barcelona. The contaminant removal efficiency of bioelectrochemical wetlands plus floating root mats is tested at different ratios (1:0, 3:1, 1:1 and 1:3, see picture May 2023) (© Clara Laguna, 2023).

Keywords

Groundwater, surface water, urban area, CEC, PFAS, trace metals, pathogens, pesticides, nutrients, nature-based solutions, Mediterranean climate

Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges

- Water scarcity and prolonged drought periods and related increases in contaminant concentrations
- Flash flood phenomena in urban and peri-urban environment
- Wild fires

Current status of the case study:

- NBS solutions correctly installed, 6-month adaptation phase of plants and microorganisms commenced
- 1st and 2nd monitoring campaigns with passive samplers completed

Key intervention and objectives

Polluted urban area; Pollutants to be studied: nutrients, metals, CECs, PFAS and viruses; Monitoring systems: ceramic passive samplers for organic contaminant monitoring, passive samplers, virus passive samplers, diffusive gradients in thin films for monitoring of bioavailable trace metals,

UPWATER CS#3 - Barcelona metropolitan region, Spain	
	<p>source apportionment-modelling; Mitigation solutions: floating wetland + Zero valent iron-bioelectrochemical wetland.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Floating wetlands will be used to remove contamination with nutrients, trace metals, and CECs. The aim is to achieve improvement of treated wastewater effluent, ideally up to drinking water quality, for minimisation of environmental impacts to the underlying aquifer and the marine environment • Elaboration of effective site-specific preventive measures in participatory processes with stakeholders to produce policy recommendations
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel wetland technology will be used to remove contamination with nutrients, trace metals, and CECs. • 4 cells of 12m² each treating a maximum water flow of 20 m³/d • The ambition of the technology is to be implemented in the Besòs River and treat almost the total water volume of the Montcada i Reixac WWTP (72,000 m³/d). This would prevent groundwater pollution in the Besòs area.)
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy briefs at local/regional level - to provide evidence of harmful pollutants affecting GW with case-specific recommendations • Developed biobased solutions will be able to prevent and mitigate GW pollution to concentration levels below toxicity and water quality guideline thresholds, but at least an 90% reduction is expected for chemicals and 2-3 log units for pathogens (absolute values)
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passive sampling as monitoring technology for CEC, trace metal and virus contamination • Nature-based solutions (bioelectrochemical wetlands plus floating root mats) to treat GW pollution • Low-energy and low-cost Long Range (LoRa) sensors with zero-cost data transfer requirements for monitoring of water level, • Humidity, Photosynthetically Available Radiation, Total Solar Radiation & temperature in the unsaturated zone
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimise passive sampler technology and validate for groundwater conditions, moving from TRL 3-4, depending on sampler type, to TRL 5-7. • Validate NBS in environmental conditions to mitigate surface water pollution (CEC, pathogens and nutrients) and protect GW, moving from TRL 3 to 5 • Develop compound specific isotope analysis for CECs and in combination with ceramic passive samplers <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of novel NBS solutions which will enable the operator to i) protect GW pollution and ii) save developing and applying energy intensive chemical treatment and thus save CO2 emission equivalents for 35 Wh/m³

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost reduction of water supply. Quantification of the reduction of water supply (water transport from other catchments and treatment) in 25hm³ related the potential aquifers quality recovery Implementation of integrated passive sampling instead of traditional grab water sampling which will imply an overall cost reduction for the GW directive of 2M€/year in GW routine monitoring (market size = 15.930) Implementation of integrated passive sampling instead of traditional grab water sampling which will imply an overall cost reduction for the WFD directive of 60M€/year in WFD routine monitoring (market size = 146.510) Influence relevant local/regional and EU policy updates <p>The calculations behind the cost savings assume a cost reduction of 15–35 EUR/sample, depending on whether isotopes are included in the analysis or not, four monitoring campaigns/year in GW sampling and 12 monitoring campaigns/year in surface water sampling, and 15.930 and 146.510 sampling points for GW and surface water, respectively (Hypothesis over WISE database sources for GW and WFD reporting).</p>
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC). The Groundwater Directive (2006/118/EC). The Drinking Water Directive (EU) 2020/2184. The Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (91/271/EEC). Environmental Quality Standards Directive (2008/105/EC) Industrial Emissions Directive (2010/75/EU). REACH Regulation (1907/2006). Water Reuse Regulation (EU) 2020/741. <p>National legislation (Spain)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Law 29/1985 on water Royal Decree, RD 849/1986 on Public Water Domain RD 817/2015 on Monitoring Criteria for surface water and environmental quality standards Law 11/2005 on the National Hydrologic Plan RD 125/2007 Regulation of Hydrological Planning <p>Regional legislation (Catalonia):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legislative Decree 3/2003 on water in Catalonia Decree 86/2009 on Statutes of the Water Catalonia Agency
Policy implications	<p>Findings may be relevant to updating local policies for implementing integral water cycle management, control mechanisms of contamination risks at source and before reaching natural aquatic systems, and using NBS to treat wastewater. As water reuse and stormwater management can increase resilience in a changing climate and water demand, policies also aim to increase the use of alternative water resources, such as NBS-treated wastewater. The elaboration of effective site-specific preventive measures can further contribute to policy improvement.</p> <p>Findings from this case study may be incorporated into recommendations for improvements in existing and proposed EU policies, including the Water Framework Directive, Groundwater Directive, Drinking Water Directive, and the proposed Water Resilience Initiative, if it proceeds.</p>

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Market implications

- Close-to-market development of ceramic passive samplers (CPS) for organic contaminants and viral passive samplers (VPS) for pathogens monitoring in GW and SW. Where passive sampling can replace traditional grab sampling, significant savings can be made (see section 'Ambition at the end of the project and beyond')

The applied LoRa technologies can be adopted by water utilities for monitoring of water-related parameters in wastewater treatment plants at several steps of wastewater treatment processes using low-energy sensors of low-cost systems with zero-cost data transfer requirements.

4. Drinking water related case studies

4.1. H2OforAll case studies

H2OforAll includes one case study which is included in the presentation below:

- Case study 1 – Coimbra, Portugal, Águas de Coimbra Drinking water network

4.1.1. H2OforAll Case Study 1 - Coimbra, Portugal

H2OforAll CS#1 – Coimbra, Portugal

Figure. 4.1.1.2 – Water distribution model for the case study, developed on EPANET (© ÁGUAS DE COIMBRA, E.M.).

Figure. 4.1.1.3 – Selection of DMAs for the case study (© ÁGUAS DE COIMBRA, E.M.).

Keywords

Drinking Water, distribution network, DBPs, on-line and real-time monitoring, sensors, novel treatment technologies, online tool, prevention measures, risk assessment

Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges

- The extreme climate events (floods and droughts) have an impact in the source water quality. Moreover, the complexity of water contamination by contaminants of emerging concern is an arising problem.
- Increased organic matter due to rising temperatures.
- Algal blooms in surface water due to the temperature increase and the accumulation of nutrients.

H2OforAll CS#1 – Coimbra, Portugal	
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Currently the drinking water is of high quality. The water supply network was modelled using a hydraulic model platform. (EPANET) regarding flow rate and chlorine profiles. Optimised methodology for sensing infrastructure placing.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Águas de Coimbra (AC) is a municipal company that provides essential public services of drinking water distribution as well as wastewater and stormwater drainage in Coimbra, Portugal. AC encompasses 13 drinking water distribution systems (132 DMA) with 87.000 clients and 1200 km of pipelines. For the purpose of the case study 3 DMAs were selected for sampling and testing. Online monitoring in real time was carried out at ARZILA site.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding & monitoring DBPs and their spread through drinking water distribution systems. Development of breakthrough water treatments to remove DBPs or avoid their formation during water disinfection processes, paying attention to their life cycle analysis, costs and risks. Establishing preventive measures for water protection engaging public and key stakeholders. Develop new protocols for toxicity and cytotoxicity assessment to rank DBPs based on their potential human health and ecosystems impact.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>Targeted potential users: Utilities companies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The results can be replicated to other water utilities with due adaptation.
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowing the chlorine concentration along the distribution networks makes it possible to predict the probability of DBPs formation since there is a relationship between chlorine concentrations and the formation of DBPs. Water Quality Models: With the water quality models developed, Águas de Coimbra will be able to predict the spread of chlorine concentrations along the distribution network. This enables the making of re-chlorination injection plans with the minimal chlorine necessary and, consequently, less formation of DBPs. (New Prevention measure) Adoption of Water quality Models as a standard prevention measure to mitigate spread of DBPS and chlorine injection Novel sensors will be developed to monitor water quality. Spectroscopic based sensors will be designed to follow up the concentration of specific DBPs while auxiliary sensors will be applied to monitor water environmental parameters (pH, dissolved oxygen). These parameters will be correlated with the probability of DBPs occurrence. A sensing infrastructure will be developed using the sensors and will incorporate real-time monitoring capabilities. An algorithm was developed to intelligently place the infrastructure in the water distribution network. New protocol for toxicity and cytotoxicity assessment. DBPs ranking based on their toxic effect potential. Innovative technologies for water treatment, disinfection and DBPs removal.

H2OforAll CS#1 – Coimbra, Portugal	
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Current: TRL 4 (Technology validated in laboratory) Expected: TRL 5 (Technology validated at Águas de Coimbra site Arzila), TRL 6 (Technology demonstrated in relevant environment) & TRL 7 (System prototype demonstration in operational environment). Infrared sensor; mid-infrared (MIR); optical sensor technology; drinking water monitoring; membrane enrichment; silver halide fiber; mid-infrared fiberoptic evanescent wave sensor (MIR-FEWS); attenuated total reflection (ATR). IR-ATR (temporary name) analyser; Laboratory scale towards application level; the sensor will be validated for the specific deployment within a controlled environment at a water distribution network. Development of suitable materials for DBPs adsorption: tested at bench-scale and a pilot unit will be assembled for validation. Evaluation of advanced oxidation technologies for the removal of DBPs precursors from water before the disinfection step: tests at lab-scale. Intermittent chlorination and UV-based technologies to reduce the amount of chlorine applied in the disinfection step: lab-scale tests and validation at a pilot scale.
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation of the Central Knowledge Base (CKB) online tool, publicly available to regulators and stakeholders as a decision support tool involving information about DBPs occurrence and toxicity. Validated sensing system involving DBPs and non-target parameters able to predict the potential occurrence of DBPs. New protocol for toxicity and cytotoxicity assessment. Novel technologies to treat and disinfect source water and remove DBPs. Preventive measures based on good practices analysis. Public engagement and awareness. Utilities companies to adopt the developed technology.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drinking water directive (EU) 2020/2184 Urban wastewater directive (EU) 2014/3019
Policy implications	<p>The information to be obtained regarding DBP formation, fate and impact will permit to establish policy recommendations about drinking water quality, standard and thresholds for new unregulated DBPs.</p> <p>Development of technologies for DBP precursors and DBP removal from water as well as new disinfection strategies that may be recommended for drinking water management.</p>
Market implications	<p>H2OforAll will develop new water monitoring and treatment technologies with market potential with interest to stakeholders (regulators, water supply companies, and the relevant stakeholders through workshops and other events will potentiate the exploitation of the technologies.</p>

4.2. intoDBP case studies

Spain, Ireland, and Cyprus are some of the countries in Europe where THMs abundance is the highest, but also complement each other well in terms of the nature of DBP precursors in the source water (natural vs anthropogenic), setting (rural vs urban), climate (dry vs humid), treatment (basic vs advanced) and disinfection strategy (chlorination vs chloramination).

intoDBP includes four case studies which are presented below :

- Case study 1 – Limassol, Cyprus – High variability of source water and quality and high formation of THMs.
- Case study 2 – Barcelona, Spain – High THMs formation potential in distributed water and changing conditions in the source reservoirs.
- Case study 3 – Madrid, Spain – Potential formation of N-DBPs from suboptimal generation of chloramines.
- Case study 4 – County Mayo, Ireland – High formation of THMs and peatland dominated catchments.

4.2.1. intoDBP Case Study 1 – Limassol, Cyprus

intoDBP CS#1 - Limassol, Cyprus	
	High variability of source water and quality and high formation of THMs
Location	Limassol, Cyprus
Pictures illustrating the case study	<p>The map shows the Limassol area in Cyprus with several key locations highlighted in yellow boxes: Kouris Dam (northwest), DWTP (north-central), Zone 2 Tank (east), and DMA 230 (southeast). The map also shows various districts and municipalities, including Spitali, Palaioi, and Ypsonas.</p>
	<p><i>Figure. 4.2.1.1. Overview of the Limassol Case Study Site (@ Limassol District Local Government Organisation)</i></p>

intoDBP CS#1 - Limassol, Cyprus

Figure. 4.2.1.2. Location of the sensors: outlet of the LWDTP, outlet of the rechlorination tank, inlet and network of the district metering area (DMA)230 (@ Limassol District Local Government Organisation)

Figure. 4.2.1.3. Process flow diagram of the Limassol DWTP (@Limassol District Local Government Organisation)

Keywords

Drinking Water, DBP, DBPs minimisation, monitoring technologies, hard sensors, fluoro-absorbance sensors, bioreporters, UV-VIS sensors, treatment technologies, MITO3X®, soft sensors, modelling, digital tools, hydraulic modelling, human exposure to DBPs, algorithmic models, full-scale DBP monitoring strategy in DWTP and DWDN

Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges

- Rising DBP precursor levels and formation.
- Decreased surface water availability, quality.
- Deteriorating catchment hydrology, soil biogeochemistry.
- High DOM content from catchment soils or phytoplankton blooms.

intoDBP CS#1 - Limassol, Cyprus

Current status of the case study:

- Sampling of DBPs and DBP formation potential and other parameters across the LDWTP and the LDWDN during 4 sampling campaigns in summer and winter.
- Completed construction, telecommunication, sensor installation, and data visualization for LDWDN's automated monitoring system.
- Progressing on ICT architecture and data acquisition system plans for the automated monitoring system.
- Ongoing hydraulic modeling and calibration, plus developing a water quality simulator for DBP fate estimation in the network.
- Developed MITO3X® Piping and Instrumentation Drawing for CS Limassol.
 - [MITO3X® technology](#) is capable of dosing and mixing liquid and gaseous reagents in a liquid flow. The technology is characterised by a series of injectors positioned on flange injection modules which ensure the optimised release of the reagents required by the process through the use of peristaltic pumps operated by an advanced management algorithm, based on fluorescence sensors and neural networks managed by an industrial computing processor in direct communication with the PLC. Currently, the technology allows for the dosing of up to eight liquid and gaseous reagents selected based on laboratory tests conducted on the real matrix. In intoDBP, MITO3X® will be adapted to the DW applications, the first application has been carried out in wastewater context.

Figure. 4.2.1.4. Concept of MITO3X® technology (@AquaSoil)

- Results of the survey conducted in Limassol on consumer habits regarding tap water have been analysed and a manuscript is currently in progress.

Key intervention and objectives

The case study involves the Limassol Drinking Water Treatment Plant (LDWTP) and the Water Distribution Network of Limassol (LDWDN). A MITO3X® pilot plant with fluoro-absorbance sensors will optimise pre-oxidation at LDWTP. In the LDWDN, four stations with UV-VIS sensors, 2 bioreporters and 2 fluorescence tools will monitor DBP transformation and model DBP formation. The study aims to understand human exposure to DBPs beyond THMs at the CS level and investigate the impact of climate change on DBP concentrations at LDWTP outflow. A survey on drinking water consumption is also carried out in the region.

- Install a MITO3X® pilot plant with fluoro-absorbance sensors at LDWTP for pre-oxidation optimisation and upgrade LDWTP water treatment trains.

intoDBP CS#1 - Limassol, Cyprus	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gain new insights into human exposure to DBPs beyond THMs and patterns of tap water consumption, and investigate the impact of climate change on DBP concentrations from LDWTP outflow. Install four stations with UV-VIS sensors, 2 bioreporters and 2 fluorescence tools in the LDWDN and develop models to track DBP transformations.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Limassol Drinking Water Treatment Plant (LDWTP) capacity is 80.000 m³/day. It receives water from the Kouris reservoir and upon treatment, it supplies clean water to the city of Limassol, villages west of Limassol, and the British Base of Akrotiri. The Drinking Water Distribution Network of Limassol (LDWDN) serves 110,000 consumers with an annual demand of 17 million m³. The pilot covers a residential area with approximately 4663 consumers and a daily average demand of 1600 m³. <p>The adoption of the intoDBP monitoring strategy for DW and DWDN, is extendable to other European utilities.</p>
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop fluorescence-based tools and bioreporter prototypes for utility DW quality monitoring, with algorithms for UV-VIS sensors to predict DBP formation. Utilities adopt full-scale monitoring strategy using UV-VIS, fluorescence tools, and bioreporters. Three DWTPs adopt MITO3X®-DW technology, expecting reduced DBP formation in CS sites. DBP precursor characterisation for DW utilities. DW distribution networks adopt full-scale monitoring strategy, covering at least 80% of the network.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hard sensors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fluoro-absorbance sensors: a prototype fluorescence tool based on on-line models will be developed to predict/monitor the formation of DPBs in water reservoirs, DWTPs and DWDNs. (start TRL 3; expected TRL 5) Bioreporters: bioreporter-based prototype on-line sensors will be designed to measure general and specific toxicity in DWDNs and DWTPs. (start TRL 2; expected TRL 4) UV-VIS sensors: commercial UV-VIS sensors from the company BADGER METER AUSTRIA are designed for online monitoring of water quality parameters in clean media. A new application will be developed: predicting DBPs and analysing the DBP formation potential of raw water sources. (start TRL 3; expected TRL 5) Soft sensors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydraulic modelling for DBP fate estimation: the developed model will assess the performance for optimal control and minimisation of risk of DBP formation to assist in the decision-making process for case-specific DWDN (start 3; expected TRL 5) Treatment technologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MITO3X® pilot plant for pre-oxidation optimization: MITO3X® technology will be adapted to the pre-oxidation to reduce DBP formation. Different pre-oxidants and

intoDBP CS#1 - Limassol, Cyprus	
	adsorbents for reducing the DBP precursors will be investigated (start TRL 3; expected TRL 6)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimise DBP formation and human exposure through source water protection, treatment optimisation, and enhanced monitoring at CS sites, aiming for a 50% reduction and achieving >30% savings in electrical energy and reagent costs. Define optimal implementation conditions at each CS for full-scale technology deployment and integrate DBP prediction algorithm into BADGER METER AUSTRIA commercial UV-VIS sensors. Patent and license developed technologies (fluorescence/absorbance sensors and MITO3X®-DW) and apply models to predict DBP occurrence. Describe temporal THM concentration and climate variables patterns, and enhance knowledge on human DBP exposure at the EU level. <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Serve as a model for DWTPs requiring chemical disinfection. Develop monitoring strategies applicable to DWN across Europe. Advance understanding of water pollution sources in a global, changing climate. Promote tap water over bottled water. Reduce bladder cancer related to THM by up to 5% in Europe. Spin-off opportunity for DBP formation consultancy.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC Drinking Water Directive 2020/2184/EC <p>Cypriot legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality of Water for Human Consumption Law, 2023 (Law No. 46(I)/2023) Water Protection and Management (Amendment) Act 2015 (No. 159(I)/2015)
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improvement of DBP legislation.
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create new market for online DBP sensors and climate change forecasting models. Develop patents for bioreporter, hardware, algorithm, MITO3X® DW technology and fluorescence/absorbance sensors for online use Incorporate DBP prediction algorithm into BADGER METER AUSTRIA's commercial UV-VIS sensors. License developed algorithms to utilities for DBP prediction in WDN. Potential spin-off for DBP consultancy based on dissolved organic fingerprint.

4.2.2. intoDBP Case Study 2 – Barcelona, Spain

intoDBP CS#2 - Barcelona, Spain	
	High THMs formation potential in distributed water and changing conditions in the source reservoirs
Location	Barcelona and its metropolitan area, Spain
Pictures illustrating the case study	<p>Figure. 4.2.2.2. Overview of the activated carbon filters of the Ter DWTP (@ Ente de Abastecimiento de Agua Ter-Llobregat (ATL))</p>

intoDBP CS#2 - Barcelona, Spain

Figure. 4.2.2.3. Overview of the settling tanks of the Ter DWTP (@ Ente de Abastecimiento de Agua Ter-Llobregat (ATL))

<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Drinking Water, DBP, DBPs minimisation, monitoring technologies, hard sensors, fluoro-absorbance sensors, bioreporters, UV-VIS sensors, treatment technologies, MITO3X®, soft sensors, full-scale DBP monitoring strategy in DWP, DWTP, modelling, digital tools, algorithmic models, DW sources, catchment protection, DOM forecasting tool, emerging DBP predictive models, human exposure to DBPs, risk assessment to DBP formation risk</p>
<p>Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising DBP precursor levels and formation. • Decreased surface water availability, quality. • Deteriorating catchment hydrology, soil biogeochemistry. • High DOM content from catchment soils or phytoplankton blooms.
<p>Current status of the case study:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sampling of DBPs and DBP formation potential and other parameters across the TDWTP and the distribution system during 4 sampling campaigns in summer and winter. • MITO3X® Piping and Instrumentation Drawing of CS Barcelona has been developed. • 3 UV-VIS sensors have been installed at TDWTP. • Experiments have been conducted, and algorithms are currently being developed to predict DBP formation using UV-VIS and fluorescence signals. • Results of the survey conducted in the metropolitan area of Barcelona regarding exposure to DBPs have been analysed and a manuscript is currently in progress. • Databases on THMs and climate variables for Barcelona CS have been analysed.
<p>Key intervention and objectives</p>	<p>The case study focuses on the Ter Drinking Water Treatment Plant (TDWTP) in Barcelona and its surrounding area. Interventions include installing a MITO3X® pilot plant with fluoro-absorbance sensors at TDWTP for pre-oxidation optimisation and placing a fluorescence sensor in the Ter water source reservoir to develop Dissolved Organic Matter (DOM) forecasting tool. The study aims to understand human exposure to DBPs</p>

intoDBP CS#2 - Barcelona, Spain	
	<p>beyond THMs at the CS level and the impact of climate change on DBP concentrations at TDWTP outflow.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Install MITO3X® pilot plant with fluoro-absorbance sensors at TDWTP for pre-oxidation optimisation. • Implement a novel approach to upgrade TDWTP water treatment, minimising DBP formation. • Develop a risk assessment methodology for DBP formation across Europe, investigate climate change effects on DBP concentrations at TDWP outflow, and create predictive models for emerging DBPs.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ter Drinking Water Treatment Plant (TDWTP) supplies Barcelona and metropolitan area since 1966, with a capacity of 691,200 m³/day. • TDWTP sources water from Ter River catchment and uses chlorine for disinfection. • ATL utility provides 6 online THM analysers (since 2015) and 3 UV-VIS sensors at TDWTP and in the WDN. <p>Repliation potential:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of intoDBP monitoring strategy for DWP. • Adoption of forecasting models for DOM content predictions in European source waters.
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop new fluorescence-based tools and bioreporter prototypes for utilities to monitor drinking water quality, and algorithms for UV-VIS sensors to predict DBP formation. • Full-scale adoption by DW utilities of the monitoring strategy combining UV-VIS, fluorescence tools, and bioreporters, with 3 DWTPs implementing the MITO3X®-DW technology to reduce DBP formation. • Characterise DBP precursors, develop a risk assessment methodology for DBP formation across Europe, and propose catchment-based source protection measures for water utilities and the EC.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard sensors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fluoro-absorbance sensors: a prototype fluorescence tool based on on-line models will be developed to predict/monitor the formation of DPBs in water reservoirs, DWTPs and DWDNs. (start TRL 3; expected TRL 5) • Bioreporters: bioreporter-based prototype on-line sensors will be designed to measure general and specific toxicity in DWDNs and DWTPs. (start TRL 2; expected TRL 4) • UV-VIS sensors: commercial UV-ViS sensors from the company BADGER METER AUSTRIA are designed for online monitoring of water quality parameters in clean media. A new application will be developed: predicting DBPs and analysing the DBP formation potential of raw water sources. (start TRL 3; expected TRL 5) • Soft sensors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydraulic modelling for DBP fate estimation: the developed model will assess the performance for optimal control and minimisation of risk of DBP formation to assist in the

intoDBP CS#2 - Barcelona, Spain	
	<p>decision-making process for case-specific DWDN (start 3; expected TRL 5)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treatment technologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MITO3X® pilot plant for pre-oxidation optimization: MITO3X® technology will be adapted to the pre-oxidation to reduce DBP formation. Different pre-oxidants and adsorbents for reducing the DBP precursors will be investigated (start TRL 3; expected TRL 6)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimise DBP formation and human exposure through source water protection, treatment optimisation, and enhanced monitoring at CS sites, aiming for a 50% reduction. • Achieve significant savings (>30%) in electrical energy and reagent costs and define optimal conditions for full-scale technology deployment at each CS. Integrate the developed DBP prediction algorithm into commercial UV-VIS sensors and adopt MITO3X®-DW technology at TDWTP. • Develop and patent a fluorescence tool to predict DBP formation and create forecasting tools for the water sector to anticipate impacts of climate change and extreme events on DOM inputs to drinking water sources. <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serve as a model for DWTPs requiring chemical disinfection for distribution. • Improve understanding of water pollution sources in a changing climate. • Spin-off opportunity for DBP formation consultancy. • Promote tap water over bottled water. • Reduce bladder cancer related to THM in Europe up to 5%
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC • Drinking Water Directive 2020/2184/EC <p>Spanish legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RD 03/2023 establishing the technical-health criteria for the quality of drinking water, its monitoring, and supply. • RD 817/2015, establishing the criteria for monitoring and assessment of the state of surface waters and environmental quality standards.
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of DBP legislation. • Improvement of water source quality.
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate DBP prediction algorithm into BADGER METER AUSTRIA's commercial UV-VIS sensors. • Create new markets for online DBP sensors and climate change forecasting models. • Potential spin-off for DBP consultancy based on dissolved organic fingerprint. • Develop patents for bioreporter, hardware, algorithm, MITO3X® DW technology and fluorescence/absorbance sensors for online use.

4.2.3. intoDBP Case Study 3 – Madrid, Spain

intoDBP CS#3 – Madrid Spain	
	Formation of N-DBPs (e.g., NDMA) from suboptimal generation of chloramines.
Location	Madrid, Spain
Pictures illustrating the case study	<p data-bbox="502 2011 1327 2038">Figure. 4.2.3.2. Aerial view of the Valmayor DWTP (@ Canal de Isabel II Gestión S.A.)</p>

intoDBP CS#3 – Madrid Spain

Figure. 4.2.3.3. MITO3X® pilot plant for chloramine disinfection optimisation (@ Lydia Sáez García)

<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Drinking Water, chloramine disinfection, DBP, DBPs minimization, monitoring technologies, hard sensors, UV-VIS sensors, MITO3X®, modelling, digital tools, hydraulic modelling, algorithmic models, full-scale DBP monitoring strategy in DWTP and DWDN</p>
<p>Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising DBP precursor levels and formation. • Decreased surface water availability, quality. • Deteriorating catchment hydrology, soil biogeochemistry. • High DOM content from catchment soils or phytoplankton blooms.
<p>Current status of the case study:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sampling of DBPs and DBP formation potential and other relevant across the VDWTWP and the distribution system during 4 sampling campaigns in summer and winter. • MITO3X® pilot plant is in the VDWTWP and an experimental plan is being developed. • 1 UV-VIS sensor has been installed at the plant.
<p>Key intervention and objectives</p>	<p>The Valmayor Drinking Water Treatment Plant (VDWTWP) is managed by Canal de Isabel II since 1976, uses chloramines for disinfection. The project aims to install a MITO3X® pilot plant to optimise monochloramine vs dichloramine formation, reducing nitrosamine formation and improving drinking water quality. Data from 3 existing UV-VIS sensors installed in Madrid’s WDN will be used to validate the hydraulic model dynamics.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Install MITO3X® unit for chloramine disinfection optimisation and 2 UV-VIS sensors. • Investigate and optimise monochloramine formation.

intoDBP CS#3 – Madrid Spain	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to the approval of monochloramine under EU Biocidal Products Regulation for DW. Validate hydraulic model dynamics with UV-VIS sensor data in WDN.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Valmayor Drinking Water Treatment Plant (VDWTP) serves DW up to 2,5 million for the city of Madrid since 1976, capacity is 1,036,800 m³/day. Water source: Valmayor Reservoir. Chloramine is used as disinfectant. Canal de Isabel II provides 3 UV-VIS sensors in the WDN. <p>Generating an optimal technology to form monochloramines for disinfection offers replication potential.</p>
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development MITO3X® technology for chloramination in Aquasoil's commercial portfolio. 3 DWTPs adopt MITO3X®-DW technology, reducing DBP formation in CS sites. DBP precursors characterisation for DW utilities. DWDN to adopt monitoring strategy based on the combination of UV-VIS, fluorescence tools and bioreporters covering at least 80% of the network. Contribute to the approval of monochloramine under EU Biocidal Products Regulation for DW.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hard sensors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> UV-VIS sensors: commercial UV-VIS sensors from the company BADGER METER AUSTRIA are designed for online monitoring of water quality parameters in clean media. Treatment technologies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MITO3X® pilot plant for chloramine disinfection optimisation: the application of MITO3X® will be directed towards the optimal in-situ formation of chloramine during final disinfection, to minimise high local concentrations of chlorine vs ammonia that would lead to dichloramine formation, the reagent causing N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA) formation in this disinfection regime (start 3; expected TRL 6)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimise DBP formation, treatment optimisation, and enhanced monitoring at CS sites, aiming for a 50% reduction. Achieve >30% savings in electrical energy and reagent costs with VDWTP adopting MITO3X®-DW technology. Define optimal implementation conditions at each CS for full-scale technology deployment. Patent and license developed technologies (MITO3X®-DW) algorithms for broader application in DWTP. <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring strategy for DWDN applicable to other European water utilities.

intoDBP CS#3 – Madrid Spain	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advance understanding of global water pollution sources amidst climate change. • Contribute to approval of monochloramine under EU Biocidal Products Regulation for DW. • Promote tap water over bottled water. • Reduce bladder cancer related to THM by up to 5% in Europe.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC • Drinking Water Directive 2020/184/EC <p>Spanish legislation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RD 03/2023 establishing the technical-health criteria for the quality of drinking water, its monitoring, and supply. • RD 817/2015, establishing the criteria for monitoring and assessment of the state of surface waters and environmental quality standards.
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of DBP legislation. • Use of chloramine as disinfectant.
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patents: MITO3X® DW technology. • License developed algorithms to utilities for DBP prediction in WDN.

4.2.4. intoDBP Case Study 4 - County Mayo, Ireland

intoDBP CS#4 - County Mayo, Ireland	
	High formation of THMs from peatland dominated catchments.
Location	County Mayo, Ireland
Pictures illustrating the case study	<div data-bbox="699 719 1190 1084"></div> <p data-bbox="507 2004 1385 2056"><i>Figure. 4.2.4.3. View of the mountain stream which supplies water to Nephin Valley Scheme (@ Nephin Valley Group Water Scheme)</i></p>

intoDBP CS#4 - County Mayo, Ireland	
Keywords	Drinking Water, DBP, DBPs minimisation, hard sensors, fluoro-absorbance sensors, UV-VIS sensors, human exposure to DBP, DW sources, catchment protection, modelling, digital tools, DOM forecasting tool, emerging DBP predictive models, risk assessment to DBP formation risk
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising DBP precursor levels and formation. • Decreased surface water availability, quality. • Deteriorating catchment hydrology, soil biogeochemistry. • High DOM content from catchment soils or phytoplankton blooms.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DBP formation potential of these cases study sites investigated. • Results of the survey to investigate the habits of consumers towards tap water have been analysed and a manuscript is currently in progress. • A modeling workflow and tool for predicting short- and long-term DOM levels in drinking water sources is currently under development. • Measures to reduce DOM in source waters are under review.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>This Case Study includes a cluster of three small Group Water Schemes located in County Mayo, supplying rural communities. The utilities are co-operative schemes which are privately managed and are represented by the National Federation of Group Water Schemes, which are located near to each other in catchments, with a high peatland prevalence. The project seeks to develop a tool to forecast the effects of short- and long-term changes in climate on DOM in drinking water sources to protect drinking water quality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Install 1 UV-VIS and 1 fluorescence sensor in reservoirs which provide initial data for DOM forecasting. • Develop risk assessment methodology for DBP formation across Europe. • Propose catchment-based source protection measures for water utilities and the EC. • New insights on human exposure to DBPs beyond THMs. • Investigate the effect of climate change on DBP concentrations in the finished drinking water.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prizon, Ballyvary, Keellogues, Straide (PBKS) Scheme: Carrowmore Lough source, serves 850 households, treated with UV-chlorination. • Callow Scheme: Callow Lough source, serves 1300 homes, treated with pressurised sand filtration, UV, and chlorination. • Nephin Valley Scheme: mountain stream source, supplies 630 households, treated with medial filtration, ozonation, chlorination. <p>Replication potential for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of forecasting models for short- and long-term DOM content predictions in other European source waters. • Adoption of novel DBP-related index-based risk assessment methodology in other European source waters.

intoDBP CS#4 - County Mayo, Ireland	
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop risk assessment methodology for DBP formation across Europe. Propose catchment-based source protection measures for water utilities and the EC. Reduce THM non-compliance risk, addressing EU DBP infringements in Ireland. Develop new fluorescence-based tool and algorithms for UV-VIS sensors to predict DBP formation.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<p>Hard sensors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fluoro-absorbance sensors: a prototype fluorescence tool based on on-line models will be developed to predict/monitor the formation of DPBs in water reservoirs, DWTPs and DWDNs. (start TRL 3; expected TRL 5) UV_VIS sensors: commercial UV-VIS sensors from the company BADGER METER AUSTRIA are designed for online monitoring of water quality parameters in clean media. A new application will be developed: predicting DBPs and analysing the DBP formation potential of raw water sources. (start TRL 3; expected TRL 5) <p>Soft sensors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Algorithms to predict DBP formation: BAGDER METER AUSTRIA will incorporate the developed algorithm to predict DBP formation in their commercial UV-VIS sensors (start TRL 3; expected TRL 5) <p>Treatment technologies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Catchment-based source protection measures: a systematic review of measuresto reduce DOM in source waters. This will include a review of literature and real-world practice. (start TRL 1; expected TRL 3)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimise DBP formation and human exposure through source water protection, treatment optimisation, and enhanced monitoring at CS sites, aiming for a 50% reduction. Patenting a fluorescence tool to predict DBP formation. Integrate developed DBP prediction algorithm into BADGER METER AUSTRIA commercial UV-VIS sensors. Develop forecasting tools for the water sector to anticipate short- and long-term future impacts of climate change and extreme events on DOM inputs to DW source water. <p>Beyond the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advance understanding of global water pollution sources amidst climate change. Spin-off opportunity for DBP formation consultancy. Promote tap water over bottled water. Reduce bladder cancer related to THM by up to 5% in Europe.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC Drinking Water Directive 2020/184/EC <p>Irish legislation;</p>

intoDBP CS#4 - County Mayo, Ireland	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Services Legislation and EU (Drinking Water) Regulations 2023, S.I. No. 99 of 2023 • Water Services Acts 2007 to 2022 - This Act makes amendments to various Acts relating to water services in Ireland and in particular in relation to the Irish public water agency Uisce Éireann. • Water Environment (Abstractions and Associated Impoundments) Act 2022 (No. 48 of 2022) – This Act provides regulation of water abstraction in Ireland. • Local Government (Water Pollution) Acts 1977 to 1990 – This Act is the primary piece of legislation governing water pollution in Ireland.
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of DBP legislation. • Improvement of water source quality.
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New market for climate change forecasting models. • Incorporate DBP prediction algorithm into BADGER METER AUSTRIA's commercial UV-VIS sensors. • Patents: fluorescence/absorbance sensors with method measurements for online use. • Spin-off opportunity for DBP formation consultancy.

4.3. SafeCREW case studies

SafeCREW includes four case studies which are included in the presentation below:

- Case study 1 – Northern Germany (Hamburg & Berlin) - Near-natural non-disinfected Drinking Water Supply
- Case study 2 – Milan city (Italy) – Chlorinated Drinking Water Supply System (DWSS)
- Case study 3– Tarragona (Spain) – Chlorinated Drinking Water Supply System (DWSS)
- Case study 4 – Western Ukraine – Chlorinated Drinking Water Supply System (DWSS)

Figure 4.3. SafeCREW case studies (© Tutech Innovation GmbH)

4.3.1. SafeCREW Case Study 1 – Northern Germany (Hamburg and Berlin)

SafeCREW CS#1 - Northern Germany	
	Northern Germany (Hamburg & Berlin) Near-natural non-disinfected Drinking Water Supply
Location	Water Work Spandau (Berlin) / Water Work Curslack (Hamburg)
Pictures illustrating the case study	
September	November
March	May
<p><i>Figure. 4.3.1.1 Photos of the seasonal change of the sampled infiltration basin (© Christoph Sprenger)</i></p>	

SafeCREW CS#1 - Northern Germany

Figure. 4.3.1.2 Flow cytometer installed in well chamber (left); flow cytometer maintenance and manual measurements (right) (© Christoph Sprenger)

<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Drinking water, DW source, DBP precursors, near-natural non-disinfected DWSS; NOM monitoring, disinfection strategies, risk assessment, risk management approach, bank filtration, groundwater, surface water, DW treatment technologies, policy and regulation</p>
<p>Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Declining water availability, increasing water demand, higher temperatures, increasing concentration of dissolved organics and microorganisms in river water • Overall declining water quality as the source of DW • Elevated bacterial concentration and possible enrichment of hygienic relevant microorganisms in surface water, possible increased surface water pathogen loads and shorter hydraulic retention times (HRT) if water demand increases
<p>Current status of the case study:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-disinfected DWDN with natural infiltrated or artificially recharged groundwater as source water. • High NOM background (e.g. 3-4 mg/L DOC in Berlin's DW) • Current early-warning systems do not include online microbial monitoring. • Despite NOM changes and potential microbial growth in DWDN, utilities cannot quickly shift to chemical disinfection, due to the looming threat of massive DBP formation.
<p>Key intervention and objectives</p>	<p>Develop a future-oriented risk management approach that includes large volume sampling via ultrafiltration modules to enrich and recover relevant microorganisms, enabling their detection at very low concentrations during subsurface passage.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the early-warning system by integration of high volume (>40 L) sampling for microbial contamination and continuous flow cytometry (FCM) of bank filtrate. • Develop a climate change adaptation roadmap for currently non-disinfected DWSS with high background DOC.

SafeCREW CS#1 - Northern Germany	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapting technology: innovative porous conductive membrane for a chemical-free removal of NOM fractions that are DBP precursors.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<p>A) Berlin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drinking Water Treatment (no disinfection): Source water is bank filtrate (BF, groundwater influenced by surface water with moderate residence time in the aquifer) treated by aeration and filtration for Fe- & Mn-removal. Local water availability enhanced by managed aquifer recharge (MAR): River Havel water treated by coagulation, rapid sand filtration and infiltration into groundwater aquifers. > 3.7 million inhabitants served (whole City) 2/3 bank filtrate, 1/3 groundwater, nature-based treatment (BF & MAR), aeration, rapid sand filtration <p>B) Hamburg</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drinking Water Treatment (no disinfection): The water works pump deep well and also shallow well water. The latter are surface water impaired source waters, river Elbe. Treatment: aeration, two filtration steps (Fe- & Mn-removal), deacidification. 1.9 Mio. Inhabitants served (whole City) 100% groundwater <p>All realised ambitions can be easily transferred to other waterworks with comparable source water conditions.</p>
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategies available to provide safe drinking water with minimal DBPs in case of first-time disinfection. Strategies will recommend treatment combinations for disinfection to remove DBP precursors. Strategies will consider pipe lining material and potential reactions between residuals in the currently non-disinfected DWDN.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NOM electrosorption: Innovative conductive membrane system to reduce NOM concentration for e.g. DBP control; replication potential expected (start TRL 4; expected TRL 5): Filtration method with low energy and without chemicals Improved quantitative microbial risk assessment methods: Indicative reference cell count representing hygienically safe water based on combination of FCM and cultivation-based methods (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantification of the microbial log removal capacity for a non-disinfected scheme. A future-oriented risk management approach including microbial sensing methods applying continuous flow cytometry (FCM) as well as ultrafiltration to enrich and recover hygienic relevant microorganisms and enabling their detection at very low concentrations.

SafeCREW CS#1 - Northern Germany	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The novel capacitive membrane treatment shall be up-scaled to TRL3-5. Strategies (incl. treatment combinations) to provide safe DW with minimal DBPs, considering potential reactions between residuals in the currently non-disinfected DWDN. <p>Beyond the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Berlin and other MAR sites in Europe will implement the online field FCM measurements and reverse Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) modelling to assess future climate change induced impacts. Roadmaps developed for implementing or avoiding disinfection in DWSS with high background dissolved organic carbon (DOC) shall be included in the national portfolio of recommendations.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU Water Framework Directive (WFD), EU Drinking water directive (DWD); <p>German legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trinkwasserverordnung (Drinking Water Ordinance), DIN-DVGW technical rules
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support science based policy making for DW consumer protection Science based recommendations to revisions of DWD and DWD watch lists Increase coherence with material certification in the EU and implementation into shortlist for future DWD uptake (Art. 11) Policy brief to support unavoidable transition from non-disinfected to disinfected drinking water supply systems Policy brief regarding disinfection and DBPs
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NOM electrosorption: Innovative Membrane based process to selectively remove NOM precursor compounds to minimise DBP formation with no need of chemical dosing

4.3.2. SafeCREW Case Study 2 – Milan city, Italy

SafeCREW CS#2 - Milan, Italy	
	Milan city (Italy) Chlorinated Drinking Water Supply Systems (DWSS)
Location	Milan, Italy
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 4.3.2.1: GAC filters of Milan drinking water treatment plant. (© MM spa)</i></p>
Keywords	Drinking water, disinfection, DBP, NOM, monitoring of biological and chemical parameters (microorganisms, interaction of materials with water, DBP formation), soft sensor. sensor optimisation, treatment technologies, risk-based early-warning system, DWTP, DWDN, chlorinated DWSS
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<p>Main risks for drinking water supply systems arising from increasing water temperatures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excessive growth of bacteria in DWDN could increase disinfection request and impact water quality by DBP generation • Increased migration from relining resins due to higher residual chlorine levels and formation of new DBPs from leached compounds
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data from online sensors currently not processed to manage disinfection • No routine monitoring of bisphenols derived from relining epoxy-resins
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Current research is evaluating how to exploit monitoring devices for studying bacterial dynamics and communities in treated water depending on other types of treatment (adsorption, disinfection). In addition, the potential migration of bisphenol A (BPA) from epoxy resins is under investigation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking of microbiological and chemical water stability and disinfection process parameters under different operating conditions

SafeCREW CS#2 - Milan, Italy	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Characterisation of bacterial presence through FCM and passive sampling • Characterisation of DBPs of relining resins along the DWDN • Application of advanced data computing to highlight correlations and develop control strategies
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 400 active wells produce 220 million m³ of drinking water annually • Water abstracted from the aquifer is treated in 28 DWTPs • Generally undergoing activated carbon filtration and disinfection via NaOCl • DWDN is about 2.228 km long, serving 1.4 Mio. Inhabitants <p>Replication potential:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of Milan strategies by other national and international water utilities
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimised set of sensors for disinfection management • Increase of microbial contamination detection probability • Monitoring plan for relining resins
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passive sampler for effective microbial monitoring for early-warning (start at idea stage, expected TRL 3 (proof of concept)) • Cellulose-based nanosponges as novel adsorption materials for the removal of DBP and DBP precursors • Optimisation of disinfection operating parameters based on online sensors and the exploitation of advanced computing (e.g. machine learning) for process control • Soft sensors to model target parameters by measuring easy-to-measure parameters to be used as backbone of an early-warning system • Integrated risk assessment weighing pathogens and DBP (no TRL applicable)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimisation of disinfection operating parameters based on a process control integrated framework • Prediction of DBPs formation following residual chlorine and relining resins interactions • Guidelines for selection and commissioning of relining resins to minimise DBPs. <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of consumer's safety by coupling online monitoring and lab analyses • Integrating guidelines for relining resins into the asset management strategy of Milan City.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drinking Water Directive 2020/184/EC <p>Italian legislation:</p>

SafeCREW CS#2 - Milan, Italy	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D.L.gs 18/2023 (Italy)
Policy implications	Building a network of water utilities for good laboratory practice (GLP) and guidelines sharing
Market implications	Market orientation towards more sustainable resins and new sensors development

4.3.3. SafeCREW Case Study 3 – Tarragona, Spain

SafeCREW CS#3 – Tarragona, Spain	
	<p>Tarragona (Spain) Chlorinated DWSS</p>
Location	Tarragona, Spain
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p><i>Figure 4.3.3.1: Aerial view of the l'Ampolla Water Treatment plant (© Consorci d'Aigües de Tarragona)</i></p>

SafeCREW CS#3 – Tarragona, Spain

Figure 4.3.3.2: Close look of the flocculation-sedimentation facilities at l'Ampolla Water Treatment plant. (© Consorci d'Aigües de Tarragona)

Figure 4.3.3.3: On-line lab facilities at l'Ampolla Water Treatment plant. (i): Turbidity measurements for the flocculation-sedimentation lines. (ii) UV-254 measurements (©t Consorci d'Aigües de Tarragona)

Keywords

Drinking water, disinfection, DBP, chlorinated DWSS, NOM, DBP formation, seasonal NOM monitoring, online monitoring technologies, sensors, soft sensors, digital tools, DBP prediction modelling DWTP, DWDN, NOM removal treatment technologies, risk assessment, early-warning system based on combined performance indicators for chemical, microbial and toxicity risks, surface water catchment

Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges

Main risks arising from climate change:

- River surface water has high seasonal variations.
- Increasing of severe droughts and storms affect water quality.
- Increasing temperature increases DBP formation and bacterial growth.

SafeCREW CS#3 – Tarragona, Spain	
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manual DWTP and DWDN set-point operation based on discrete sampling, which cannot guarantee compliance with the EU DWD at all points of supply. DWTP set-points based on total organic carbon (TOC) values, without knowledge of NOM composition and final DBP formation. Setting DWDN chlorination booster set-points without knowledge of effect on DBP formation. No studies on the specific threats due to climate change are available to take actions in DWTPs or DWDNs.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>(I) In-depth evaluation on how changes in DWTP processes result in reduced DBP formation potential not only by lowering the NOM quantity but also by changing NOM chemical properties.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate the seasonal NOM quantity and composition and treatment removal capacity to minimise DBP formation. Implement new treatment strategies to optimise NOM removal. <p>(II) Development of an early alert system predicting the final generation of DBPs from the expected influent water to the DWTP, and recommend process changes to prevent formation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop new in-network DBP formation prediction model based on combining mechanistic and data-driven models. Develop risk assessment tools for optimising NOM removal and chlorination boosting in the network minimising DBP formation. <p>(III) Risk-based management of the DWTP and DWDN which combines chemical, toxicity and microbial risk</p>
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DWTP treating water from Ebro river and serving 800.000 inhabitants with a 400 km distribution network. DWTP includes pre-ozonation, flocculation, sand filtration, main-stage ozonation, activated carbon filtration, ultraviolet disinfection and final disinfection with NaOCl. Chlorination boosters along the network to keep residual free chlorine. <p>Replicability potential</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Via knowledge transfer to other DWSS with surface water catchments. Knowledge and solutions will be useful for DWDN with chlorination and chlorination boosters.
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimal risk-based management of the DWTP and DWDN which combines chemical, toxicity and microbial risk
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online THM analyser with differentiation of the 4 main THMs (start TRL 3, expected TRL 7) Soft sensors for DWTP and DWDN to model DBP target parameters by measuring easy-to-measure parameters. Combination of different AOP techniques for optimal settings for transformation of DBP precursors (start TRL 3, expected TRL 4)

SafeCREW CS#3 – Tarragona, Spain	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New in-network DBP formation prediction model based on combining mechanistic and data-driven models (verified at project end, TRL not applicable). • Early alert systems and risk assessment tools for optimising NOM removal and chlorination boosting in the network minimising DBP formation. • Optimal risk-based and cost-efficient management of the DWTP and DWDN which combines chemical, toxicity and microbial risk
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-depth knowledge of the effect of DWTP processes on reduced DBP formation. • Develop an early alert system predicting expected DBPs and recommending process changes. • Risk-based management of the DWTP and DWDN which combines chemical, toxicity and microbial risk <p>Beyond the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer to other DWSS with surface water catchments. • The relationship between NOM, treatment and DBPs could trigger focus on new treatment processes.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Drinking Water Directive (DWD); <p>Spanish legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spanish Drinking water regulation (RD 3/2023)
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of DBP legislation. • Introduction of risk assessment-based legislation.
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The relationship between NOM, treatment and DBPs could trigger focus on new treatment processes. • Risk-based management relying on network modelling could promote the digitalisation of other DWDNs.

4.3.4. SafeCREW Case Study 4 – Western Ukraine

SafeCREW CS#4 – Western Ukraine	
Drinking water distribution network in western Ukraine	
Location	Western Ukraine
Pictures illustrating the case studies	
Keywords	Drinking water, disinfection, DBP, DWSS; DWDN; groundwater; bank filtration, managed aquifer recharge, monitoring, risk-based management, water safety plan, soft sensors, replication site , regulation
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The extreme climate events (floods and droughts) have an impact on the source water quality and amount of water. Moreover, there is no experience in applying modern methods of predicting the dissemination of pollution in drinking water supply systems.
Current status of the case study:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research at the initial stage

Figure 4.3.4.1: Model of the drinking water distribution network of western Ukraine. (© S. Martynov, NUWEE)

SafeCREW CS#4 – Western Ukraine	
Key intervention and objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing risk-based management through the creation of Water Safety Plans (WSP). • Adapting hydraulic models and establishing soft sensors for conditions with limited data availability. • Identifying regulatory and real-life gaps in Ukrainian and European drinking water quality guideline values.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • About 98% of cities, 91% of urban-type settlements and 23% of villages are covered by centralised water supply system services in Ukraine. • The total length of water supply networks is 92 thousand km, including 35% of dilapidated and emergency networks. • Operating systems of centralised water supply in settlements of western Ukraine mainly use ground waters. <p>The results can be replicated to other water utilities in Ukraine with due adaptation.</p>
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information on riverbank filtration: operational practices, hydrogeological properties and water quality monitoring data will be compiled. • A risk-based assessment on a selected RBF site will be performed to identify further investigations required to reduce the uncertainty of risks and to implement remediation measures. • The ready-to-use risk-based management tool ability to predict spatial and temporal behaviour of free chlorine and DBP species formed, their risks to human health, and actions for reducing their presence will be explored with respect to the envisaged association of Ukraine to the EU and the implementation of the EU DWD.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapting hydraulic models and establishing soft sensors for conditions with limited data availability from SafeCREW CS#2 and CS#3. • Monitoring of water quality indicators in the water supply source and water supply networks to predict the spread of chemical and microbiological contaminants.
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public engagement and awareness
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Drinking water directive (DWD), Urban wastewater directive; <p>Ukrainian legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ukrainian law 'On drinking water and drinking water supply' • Water Strategy of Ukraine for the period up to 2050

SafeCREW CS#4 – Western Ukraine

Policy implications

Increasing knowledge in the field of drinking water supply in connection with respect to the envisaged association of UA to the EU and the implementation of the EU DWD

Market implications

For transferring and applying the results of SafeCREW in Ukraine, and enabling further collaboration at national and European levels, a concept for the non-profit Center of Excellence in Water Management (CEWM), which would bridge the gap in water related applied R&I activities and foster close cooperation of R&I institutes and water utilities in Ukraine, will be prepared.

The approach of the CEWM to overcome gaps in the Ukrainian water sector by strengthening applied research and education will be summarised in a roadmap, to assist in seeking post-SafeCREW funding at national, EU and international level, and for water utilities interested in collaborating with the CEWM.

4.4. ToDrinQ case studies

ToDrinQ includes five case studies which are included in the presentation below:

- Case study 1 - Amsterdam, Netherlands
- Case Study 2 - Athens, Greece
- Case Study 3 - Val de Bagnes, Switzerland
- Case Study 4 - Beaune, France
- Case Study 5 - Prague, Czechia

4.4.1. ToDrinQ Case Study 1 - Amsterdam, Netherlands

ToDrinQ CS#1 - Amsterdam, Netherlands	
	Demonstrating solutions in Amsterdam
Location	Drinking water treatment utility Leiduin near Amsterdam
Pictures illustrating the case study	<p data-bbox="555 1888 1270 1917"><i>Figure 4.4.1.1. Drinking Water Treatment Plant Leiduin (© Waternet)</i></p>
Keywords	Drinking Water, water quality monitoring, PFAS removal; hard sensor testing: ammonium, lead, total cell counts, fecal indicators; soft sensor

ToDrinQ CS#1 - Amsterdam, Netherlands	
	testing: turbidity, NOM and metals, coagulation, ozone optimisation; design support tool; modular platform; DW sources, DW treatment
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing source water quality due to climate change and pollution • Changing water demand due to population growth • Changing water demand due to economic developments
Current status of the case study:	<p>The Case study is half way (third year)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial deployment and testing of hard sensors in progress • Soft sensors under development with user requirements defined • Pilot unit design under development, and installation preparations will be soon underway • Design support tool under development by the respective partner • FIWARE modular platform in concept
Key intervention and objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research an efficient, cost effective and sustainable process for PFAS removal • Apply hard sensors to optimise operation • Develop soft sensors to predict raw water quality and to optimise operations • Support development of alternative treatment trains for different types of water sources and raw water quality characteristics by using the design support tool • Provide input to the modular platform to improve, in real-time, operations of water intake, conveyance, treatment and distribution, and support informed decisions when unexpected situations occur <p>The presence of PFAS in the sources for drinking water is a problem for drinking water companies, especially for those using surface water. Therefore, in the ToDrinQ project the focus is on application of new innovative adsorbents which can reach the low (future) PFAS standard.</p> <p>Hard sensors are tested for e.g. for total cell counts in the influent and effluent of slow sand filters and faecal indicators in all steps of the drinking water treatment.</p> <p>There are two soft sensors and two reinforced learning models dedicated for the case study: The soft sensor focus on forecasting of turbidity of raw water from the Lek Canal at the DW pretreatment, and on predictions of the ozonation process of at the DWTP Leiduin. The reinforced learning models will be implemented for operational support of the coagulation and the ozonation step in the treatment train.</p> <p>The design-support tool for flexible drinking water treatment plant generates and evaluates alternative treatment trains for different types of water sources and raw water quality characteristics.</p> <p>Building on elements of past work will integrate real-time data on water quality from the entire system and support early-warning, risk assessment and risk management. The new modular platform is expected to improve operations of water intake, conveyance, treatment and distribution, and support informed decisions when unexpected situations occur.</p>

ToDriQ CS#1 - Amsterdam, Netherlands	
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensors will be tested in full-scale treatment and in a slow sand filtration pilot plant Drinking water treatment concerns treatment of surface water and PFAS removal will be tested on pilot scale Design support tool will cover alternative treatment trains for different types of water sources and raw water quality characteristics The modular platform covers, in real-time, operations of water intake, conveyance, treatment and distribution, and support informed decisions when unexpected situations occur. <p>Replicability potential:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A PFAS-removal technology will enable drinking water utilities to comply with PFAS standards Hard sensors and soft sensors will enable drinking water companies to optimise operations The design support tool and modular platform gives possibilities for drinking water utilities to deal with uncertainties, both I design and in operations
Expected outcomes	<p>PFAS removal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using the selected adsorbent, it will be clear whether the new PFAS standards can be met at pilot scale. Optimising the process conditions (empty bed contact time, type of adsorbent, regeneration procedure), the costs and environmental effects of introducing this new treatment step in drinking water production will be limited and comparable or lower than alternative treatment technologies for PFAS removal (ion exchange, reverse osmosis). <p>Hard sensors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IonSens ammonium analyses in the influent and effluent of the rapid sand filters gives the opportunity to anticipate on a declining nitrification in the filters at a low water temperature Using the MetalSens from OliSense for lead analysis makes it possible to determine exposure to elevated lead concentrations in drinking water released from appendages or in house plumbing The online flow cytometer (BactoSense) from bNovate makes it possible to follow the ripening of slow sand filters Using the Udetect from Orvion (total cell counts and faecal indicators) may give a better direct and real-time indication of the required disinfection capacity of each treatment step in the drinking water production scheme <p>Soft sensors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The implementation of these models is expected to significantly enhance operational efficiency and water quality management, by diminishing the dosage of ferric chloride during coagulation and optimising the dosage of ozone for effective pathogens removal and controlled formation of bromate and biodegradable organic carbon. <p>Modular platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improvement in access to real-time insights in development of water quality in the drinking water supply chain, support to interventions in the drinking water supply chain, and ultimately, increasing reliability of the drinking water supply chain and reducing costs and use of chemicals

ToDrinQ CS#1 - Amsterdam, Netherlands	
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard sensors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #1: PestiSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5-6) • #2.1: MetalSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 6) • #2.2: IonSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 6) • #3: Udetect semi-automatic (start TRL 3, end TRL 8) • #4: BactoSense (start TRL 3, end TRL 6-7) • #5: Concentration tool for microbiological sensors (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5) • Soft sensors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #6: Estimation of turbidity of the coagulation-flocculation process (start TRL 3-4, expected TRL 6-7) • #7: Early prediction of turbidity in Drinking Water Treatment Plant inlet (start TRL 2, expected TRL 5) • #8: Prediction of the ozonation exposure (CT) to improve the ozonation process (start TRL 2, expected TRL 5) • Reinforcement Learning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #1: Optimise coagulant (ferric chloride) dosage in flocculation/coagulation process (start TRL 2, expected TRL 5) • Advanced, cost-effective drinking water treatment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PFAS removal (start TRL 1, expected TRL 5) • Design support Tool for drinking water treatment plants (start TRL 1, expected TRL 5) • Integrated modular platform for risk-based decision support for drinking water supply (start TRL 1, expected TRL 5)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With respect to the PFAS removal technology, the exploitation of the new adsorption process is foreseeable as the present technology for PFAS removal in the drinking treatment scheme, granular activated carbon filtration, requires a high reactivation frequency for PFAS removal which is expensive, results in a high CO₂-footprint, • With respect to the hard sensors, especially the total cell counts and faecal indicators (BactoSense and Udetect) offer additional information to guarantee the microbial drinking water quality and to optimise the operations. Exploitation of these sensors in the operations of Waternet is expected, • With respect to the design support tool, alternative treatment trains for different types of water sources and raw water quality characteristics can be generated and evaluated, • With respect to the modular platform, it will give advice on optimal control and risk management interventions throughout the water supply chain, based on predictions of quality at the source and assessed variations in water quality during conveyance, treatment and distribution. <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The outcomes of the demo Case Amsterdam contribute to the toolkit for adaptable resilient installations securing high quality drinking water
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2020/2184 European drinking water directive <p>Netherlands legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dutch drinking water directive

ToDrinQ CS#1 - Amsterdam, Netherlands	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provisional guideline of the Dutch Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) for PFAS in drinking water
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of hard sensors and soft sensors additional to pre-described analytical methods in the European Drinking Water Directive
Market implications	<p>Hard sensors and soft sensors offer an alternative for laboratory analysis using laboratory equipment.</p> <p>The design support tool and the modular platform will be disseminated for open use in water companies, making design of treatment plants more transparent and operation more reliable.</p> <p>An alternative solution for PFAS removal may enrich the conventional treatment philosophy and become part of innovative treatment trains.</p>

4.4.2. ToDrinQ Case Study 2 - Athens, Greece

ToDrinQ CS#2 - Athens, Greece	
Demonstrating solutions in Athens, Greece	
Location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Polydendri Drinking Water Treatment Plant DWTP, Attica Lake Yliki
Pictures illustrating the case studies	
<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 4.4.2.1 Drinking Water Treatment Plant Polydendri (© EYDAP 2020)</i></p>	

ToDrinQ CS#2 - Athens, Greece

Figure 4.4.2.2 Lake Yliki (© EYDAP ETAIRIA PAGION, 2000)

Figure 4.4.2.3 Unmanned Surface Vehicles for testing water (INTCATCH) (© EYDAP R&D Archives)

Figure 4.4.2.4 Inside the Polydendri DWTP facilities. Location for the Athens Pilot unit (© EYDAP R&D Archives)

Keywords

Drinking Water, water quality monitoring, drinking water sources, drinking water treatment, drinking water conveyance and distribution, hard sensors, soft sensors, innovative technologies, algal bloom, MABR; design support tool; modular platform.

Key intervention and objectives

The focus is on water monitoring from the Mornos canal, Lake Yliki, and the respective boreholes, as well as on water treatment. More specifically:

- Deploy hard sensors for nitrates, ammonium, E. coli and total bacteria monitoring
- Implement soft sensors for predictive analysis of water quality

ToDrinQ CS#2 - Athens, Greece

- Install a small-scale DWTP pilot unit for testing new treatment technologies
- Develop a design-support tool for efficient water treatment plant operation
- Integrate all technologies into a FIWARE-compliant modular platform

Scale & treatment, replicability

The Athens Case Study involves the DWTP, which has a treatment capacity of 200,000 - 300,000 cubic meters per day. The plant primarily treats water from the Mornos canal, supplemented by water from Lake Yliki and the Mavrosouvala borehole during maintenance or high-demand periods. The treatment process at Polydendri DWTP includes prechlorination, screening, coagulation, sedimentation, sand filtration, and secondary chlorination.

For the ToDrinQ project, a small-scale drinking water treatment pilot unit with a capacity of 500 liters per hour will be installed within the Polydendri DWTP premises. This unit will incorporate advanced treatment technologies such as ozonation, ultrafiltration, and a Membrane Aerated Biofilm Reactor (MABR) system. The pilot unit aims to evaluate the effectiveness of these innovative treatments in improving water quality, particularly when treating water from Lake Yliki, which presents challenges such as algae blooms and slight odor due to its low water circulation and surrounding agricultural activities.

The results from this pilot unit will provide critical insights into the scalability and efficacy of these advanced treatment processes for potential full-scale implementation.

Replication potential for:

- Adoption of drinking water monitoring tools for all DW sources
- Adoption of forecasting models in source waters
- Adoption of design support tool on Greek level and beyond

Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges

- High levels of sun radiation causing algal blooms in Lake Yliki
- Agricultural runoff impacting water quality with nitrates and pesticides
- Variable water quality due to weather conditions and seasonal changes

Current status of the case study:

This information summarises the current status (half way of the project duration of 4 years):

- Initial deployment and testing of hard sensors in progress
- Soft sensors under development with user requirements defined
- Pilot unit design under development, and installation preparations will be soon underway
- Design support tool under development by the respective partner
- FIWARE modular platform has been used from EYDAP personnel in another project. Currently under expanding to include all ToDrinQ modules.

ToDrinQ CS#2 - Athens, Greece

Expected outcomes

- Improved real-time water quality monitoring, with the use of real-time monitoring technologies (hard sensors, soft sensors, satellites etc.)
- Enhanced operational efficiency of Polydendri DWTP
- Reduction in water treatment disruptions and maintenance costs by predicting algal blooms and nutrient run-offs
- Better management of water quality from source to tap
- Valuable data for future water management strategies

Key technologies and deployment (TRL)

- Hard sensors
 - #1: PestiSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5-6)
 - #2.1: MetalSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 6)
 - #2.2: IonSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 6)
 - #3: Udetect semi-automatic (start TRL 3, end TRL 8)
 - #4: BactoSense (start TRL 3, end TRL 6-7)
 - #5: Concentration tool for microbiological sensors (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5)
- Soft sensors
 - #1: Early Warning for nutrient runoff in the Yliki Lake (start TRL 4, expected TRL 5)
 - #2: Chl-a estimation (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5)
 - #3: Floating Algal Index - Bloom occurrence probability estimation (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5)
 - #4: Water Quality Index (WQI) (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5)
- Reinforcement Learning:
 - #1: Optimise coagulant (aluminium) dosage in flocculation/coagulation process (start TRL 2, expected TRL 5)
 - #2: Optimise chlorine dosage in pre-chlorination (start TRL 2, expected TRL 5)
 - #3: Optimise chlorine dosage in post-chlorination (start TRL 2, expected TRL 5)
- Advanced, cost-effective drinking water treatment
 - Treatment scheme (start TRL 2, expected TRL 6-7)
 - Design support tool for drinking water treatment plants (start TRL 1, expected TRL 5)
 - Integrated modular platform for risk-based decision support for drinking water supply (start TRL 1, expected TRL 5)

Ambition at the end of the project and beyond

- **Full Integration of Innovative Sensors:** EYDAP aims to have successfully validated and integrated the innovative hard and soft sensor technologies within its water supply and treatment network, ensuring accurate and timely water quality assessments.
- **Optimised Treatment Processes:** By leveraging the data collected from advanced sensors and treatment systems, EYDAP aims to optimise its water treatment processes. This includes adjusting chemical dosages and operational parameters based on real-time data to improve efficiency and reduce costs.

ToDrinQ CS#2 - Athens, Greece

- **Proactive Maintenance and Issue Resolution:** The integration of predictive maintenance tools and early-warning systems will allow EYDAP to identify potential issues before they escalate, minimising downtime and maintenance costs.
- **Improved Decision Support Tools:** The design-support tool tested within the project will enable EYDAP to make informed decisions regarding the planning and operation of water treatment plants, especially in response to varying water quality conditions.

Beyond the project

- **Environmental Impact Reduction:** By implementing advanced treatment technologies and optimising operational practices, EYDAP aims to reduce its environmental footprint, particularly in terms of chemical usage and energy consumption.
- **Advanced Data Analytics:** EYDAP will continue to enhance its data analytics capabilities, integrating advanced algorithms and machine learning techniques to gain deeper insights into water quality trends and operational performance.
- **Smart Water Management:** Leveraging the data collected from various sources, EYDAP aims to implement smart water management practices, optimising resource usage and improving overall system efficiency.

Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)

European legislation:

- Drinking Water Directive 2020/184/EC

Greek legislation:

- Presidential Decree 51/2007
- Law 3199/03 on water protection and the sustainable management of the water resources

Policy implications

- Support Revised European Drinking water Directive and local directives
- Improvement of DW monitoring norms

Market implications

ToDrinQ will develop new water monitoring and treatment technologies with market potential with interests to stakeholders (regulators, water supply companies, water technology industry). The involvement of several companies in the consortium as well as the involvement of relevant stakeholders through workshops and other events will potentiate the exploitation of the technologies.

4.4.3. ToDrinQ Case Study 3 - Val de Bagnes, Switzerland

ToDrinQ CS#3 - Val de Bagnes, Switzerland	
	Mayentzet, Val de Bagnes, Switzerland Testing real-time monitoring systems Bactosense and Udetect Sensor
Location	The Mayentzet is a mountainous area located in the Swiss Alps.
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p style="text-align: center; font-size: small;"><i>Figure 4.4.3.1. Drinking water treatment plant Val de Bagnes (© ALTIS)</i></p>
Keywords	Drinking Water, real-time monitoring, Bactosense, Udetect, bacteriological analysis, sensor, Mayentzet source, water reservoir, bacterial contamination, E. coli, Enterococci, specialised interface, drinking water supply, drinking water distribution network, Bacteria detection, drinking water sources, environmental monitoring
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	<p>Distance and Accessibility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The reservoir and critical monitoring points are located far from easily accessible areas. • The extensive water distribution network complicates frequent, on-site inspections and real-time data collection. <p>Untreated Water Sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two out of the three sources feeding the reservoir are untreated, increasing the risk of contamination. • Monitoring these untreated sources is crucial due to potential stability issues. <p>Bacterial Contamination:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The risk of contamination from bacteria such as E. coli and Enterococci, which are common in areas with local animal populations. • Any contamination can quickly impact public health, making rapid detection and response essential. <p>Technological Integration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring that the real-time data from Bactosense and Udetect sensors are accurately integrated and interpreted by the specialised interfaces.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dependence on the reliability and accuracy of advanced sensor technologies for critical safety information. <p>Environmental Factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Natural environmental changes or events (e.g., heavy rainfall, floods) can affect the stability and quality of water sources. Seasonal variations might impact both the bacterial load and the overall reliability of water sources. <p>Resource Allocation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The need for significant investment in equipment, technology infrastructure, and trained personnel to manage and maintain the monitoring systems. Balancing resources between routine monitoring, emergency responses, and system upgrades or expansions. <p>Data Management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Handling large volumes of real-time data requires robust data management systems and protocols. Ensuring data integrity, security, and timely analysis for actionable insights is critical. <p>These points outline the primary risks and challenges associated with the implementation and maintenance of real-time monitoring systems for the Mayentzet water source and similar case studies.</p>
Current status of the case study:	<p>This information summarises the current status (half way of the project duration of 4 years) regarding the deployment and usage of Bactosense and Udetect in the case study, highlighting key points for assessment and potential improvements.</p> <p>Bactosense Installation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bactosense has been operational for the past 6 months, providing real-time data. Operators of the water network receive alerts in case of significant contamination events. <p>Udetect Usage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The laboratory regularly utilises Udetect to analyse various samples. While the system functions effectively, the current protocol is deemed too time-consuming.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>ToDrinQ aims to enhance water quality management in the Valais region of Switzerland through the implementation of real-time monitoring systems. By utilising innovative sensors such as Bactosense and Udetect, the project seeks to provide accurate water quality data, promptly detect any bacterial contamination, and improve responsiveness to pollution events. By engaging local water utilities, regulatory authorities, and the community, the project promotes the adoption of sustainable practices and raises awareness about water resource protection. The potential implications in terms of policies, markets, and innovations are geared towards strengthening environmental protection measures and fostering proactive and efficient water resource management in the Valais region.</p> <p>The Mayentzet area contains a water reservoir fed by three water sources, which in turn supply water to the residents of Verbier. Two of these three</p>

ToDrinQ CS#3 - Val de Bagnes, Switzerland

sources are untreated, making their monitoring crucial even though they are generally very stable. However, the risk of bacterial contamination can never be entirely ruled out. This area is particularly sensitive to bacteria such as E. coli and enterococci, which originate from local animals.

Key Objectives:

- Enhance real-time monitoring of the Mayentzet water source.
- Reduce the time required for bacteriological analysis for quicker responses.
- Identify and prevent risks of bacterial contamination, particularly E. coli and enterococci.

Significant Interventions:

- Testing the Bactosense and Udetect sensors for continuous and precise surveillance.
- Integrating sensors with specialised interfaces for real-time data transmission.
- Implementing environmental monitoring systems to assess water quality and detect changes.

Key Innovations:

- Utilising advanced sensor technologies for more efficient real-time data collection.
- Integrating cutting-edge sensors for early detection of bacterial contaminations.
- Implementing automated systems for continuous monitoring and rapid response to potential incidents.

Scale & treatment, replicability

Real-time Monitoring Systems:

- Utilisation of Bactosense and Udetect sensors.
- Integration with specialised interfaces for data transmission.

Water Source Details:

- Mayentzet water source and its importance for Verbier residents.
- Fed by three distinct water sources, with two being untreated.

Bacteriological Analysis:

- Real-time data on bacterial counts per sample.
- Shortening analysis time for more immediate responses.

Bacterial Contamination Risks:

- Focus on identifying E. coli and Enterococci.
- Understanding contamination sources, mainly from local animals.

Environmental Monitoring:

- Continuous surveillance of water quality.
- Ensuring stability and safety of water sources.

Challenges:

- The large, extensive water distribution network.
- Distant location of the reservoir complicates monitoring efforts.

Key Descriptors for Other Case Studies:

- Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR)

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- Groundwater Quality
- Surface Water Monitoring
- Digital Water Management
- Public Health Safety
- Remote Sensing
- Sustainable Water Resource Management

These points and descriptors might help frame the scale and treatment aspects of various related case studies.

Replication potential:

The interventions, and innovations put in place to enhance monitoring and management of the Mayentzet water source have potential applications for other similar case studies:

- **Water Utilities:** Other water utility companies can replicate the real-time monitoring systems and sensor technology to improve water quality management and response to contamination events.
- **Regions with Similar Challenges:** Areas facing similar water quality issues, especially those with untreated water sources, can replicate the monitoring protocols and alert systems to enhance public health protection.
- **Environmental Monitoring Initiatives:** Organisations focusing on environmental monitoring and conservation can replicate the project's strategies to assess water quality and ecosystem health.
- **Policy and Regulatory Bodies:** Replicating the project's data analysis and reporting mechanisms can assist policy and regulatory bodies in developing effective water quality standards and compliance measures.
- **Community Engagement Models:** The community engagement and awareness programs implemented in this case study can be replicated in other regions to promote water conservation and sustainable water management practices.

Expected outcomes

Improved Water Quality Monitoring:

- Enhanced real-time monitoring capabilities leading to proactive contamination detection.
- Timely alerts and responses to potential water quality issues.

Enhanced Public Health and Safety:

- Reduced risks of bacterial contamination such as E. coli and enterococci.
- Minimised health hazards for residents reliant on the water supply.

Efficient Data Transmission and Analysis:

- Streamlined data transmission process for quicker decision-making.
- Improved analysis methods for more accurate and timely results.

Resource Optimisation:

- Efficient allocation of resources through targeted monitoring efforts.
- Cost savings associated with early detection and prevention measures.

Technological Advancements and Scalability:

ToDrinQ CS#3 - Val de Bagnes, Switzerland	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of advanced sensor technologies for reliable and scalable monitoring. • Potential for broader application and adaptation of similar systems in other regions or contexts.
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard Sensors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #2.2: IonSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 6) • #3: Udetect semi-automatic (start TRL 3, end TRL 8) • #4: BactoSense (start TRL 3-4, end TRL 6-7) • #5: Concentration tool for microbiological sensors (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5) • Soft Sensors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #1: Early warning for nutrient runoff in the Yliki Lake (start TRL 4, expected TRL 5) • #2: Chl-a estimation (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5) • #3: Floating Algal Index - Bloom occurrence probability estimation (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5) • #4: Water Quality Index (WQI) (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5) • #5: Early warning of bacteriological contamination in Sarayer (start TRL 2, expected TRL 5)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<p>Sustainability Goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing a self-sustaining water treatment system to ensure long-term water quality. • Implementing eco-friendly practices to reduce the project's environmental footprint. <p>Community Impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing public health and well-being through reliable access to clean drinking water. • Empowering local communities through awareness programs on water conservation and sanitation. <p>Technological Advancements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporating innovative water treatment technologies for efficient and effective operations. • Continuously evolving and adapting systems to meet future water treatment challenges. <p>Partnerships and Collaboration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening partnerships with stakeholders for ongoing support and community engagement. • Collaborating with research institutions for continuous improvement and knowledge sharing in water treatment. <p>Scalability and Replicability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing the project framework with scalability and replicability in mind for future expansion. • Serving as a model for similar water treatment initiatives in other regions, promoting sustainable practices globally.

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	<p>Beyond the project</p> <p>Knowledge Sharing and Capacity Building:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing training programs to empower local communities in water management and conservation practices. • Sharing project insights and best practices with other regions to promote sustainable water initiatives globally. <p>Research and Development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investing in ongoing research and development to enhance water treatment technologies and efficiency. • Collaborating with industry experts to drive innovation and address emerging water challenges proactively. <p>Community Resilience:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building community resilience through awareness campaigns, emergency response training, and disaster preparedness. • Fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility among community members for sustainable water practices. <p>Global Impact and Partnerships:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forming partnerships with international organisations for cross-border water management initiatives. • Contributing to global conversations on water sustainability, climate resilience, and equitable access to clean water resources.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drinking Water Directive 2020/184/EC <p>Regional legislation (Valais, Switzerland):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Valais Drinking Water Quality Standards: Regulations ensuring the quality and safety of drinking water in the Valais region. • Valais Water Master Plan: Strategic document outlining objectives and measures for sustainable water management in Valais. • Valais Water Act: Local legislation governing water resource management and conservation practices in the Valais canton.
Policy implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced Water Quality Regulations: Develop or amend policies to incorporate real-time monitoring requirements for water utilities to promptly identify and address contamination events. • Investment in Advanced Technologies: Encourage funding and support for the adoption of innovative sensor technologies in water quality management to improve monitoring precision and response times. • Community Engagement Initiatives: Implement policies that promote community involvement and awareness in water conservation and pollution prevention efforts, aligning with sustainable water management practices. • Interagency Cooperation: Facilitate collaborations between regulatory bodies, water utility companies, and environmental agencies to streamline data sharing, enhance monitoring capabilities, and ensure effective policy enforcement.

ToDrinQ CS#3 - Val de Bagnes, Switzerland

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Capacity Building Programs: Establish training programs for water utility staff and stakeholders on utilising advanced monitoring systems effectively and interpreting real-time data for informed decision-making.
Market implications	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Emergence of Advanced Water Sensor Technologies: Introduction of new products and services related to real-time water quality monitoring systems for both industrial and residential applications.• Opportunities for Sensor Technology Providers: Increased market demand for sensor technology providers to supply advanced monitoring devices and data analysis tools to water utility companies and environmental agencies.• Development of Water Management Solutions: Growth in market opportunities for companies specialising in water management solutions, including data interpretation software and predictive analytics for water quality assessment.• Expansion of Environmental Monitoring Sector: Expansion in the environmental monitoring sector, with a focus on water quality monitoring solutions, leading to new market entrants and technological advancements.• Demand for Sustainable Water Solutions: Rising demand for sustainable water solutions in the market, driving innovation in water treatment technologies and promoting eco-friendly practices in water resource management.

4.4.4. ToDrinQ Case Study 4 - Beaune, France

ToDrinQ CS#4 - Beaune, France	
	<p align="center">Demonstrating novel water quality monitoring solutions at Beaune, France</p> <p align="center">Water quality in a vineyard region</p>
<p>Location</p>	<p align="center">Beaune and Gevrey-Chambertin, France</p>
<p>Pictures illustrating the case study</p>	<div data-bbox="705 656 1161 1066" data-label="Image"> </div> <p align="center"><i>Figure 4.4.4.1. Drinking water treatment plant Beaune Bouzaise (© VeoliaEau France)</i></p> <div data-bbox="564 1158 1299 1585" data-label="Image"> </div> <p align="center"><i>Figure 4.4.4.2. Supply of Bouzaise DWTP (raw water) (© Veolia Eau France)</i></p>
<p>Keywords</p>	<p>Drinking Water, water quality monitoring, groundwater, agricultural region, karstic spring, organic micropollutants, hardness, total bacteria</p>
<p>Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural region: nitrates, pesticides • Karstic region: hardness • Water sources: deep or superficial aquifer: variations in water quality • Internal network- older sections: lead

ToDrinQ CS#4 - Beaune, France	
Current status of the case study:	<p>This information summarises the current status (half way of the project duration of 4 years):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The progress and preliminary results in the Beaune and Gevrey Chambertin case study show significant results in water quality monitoring, particularly in the onsite analysis of nitrates, chlorides and lead, across various locations and water types through the hard sensors developed in ToDrinQ. • For nitrates, measurements were conducted in Perrigny and Bouzaise, encompassing deep and low aquifers as well as treated water from filters and tanks. The reference method employed for comparison was NF EN ISO 14911 (ionic chromatography). The prototypes utilised included IS V3 and IS V3 bi-ions, with a total of 162 measurements taken into account. The results exhibited a minimal difference from the laboratory reference, with an average deviation of only 8%. The tests are complete for nitrates with IonSens current prototype. • New tests for lead with MetalSens started in fall 2024.
Key intervention and objectives	<p>Study Areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beaune: a French wine-growing commune of 22000 inhabitants. It is located between Dijon and Lyon. It is well known because it is considered as the capital of Burgundy wines. • Gevrey-Chambertin: also a French wine-growing commune of 4500 inhabitants. It is located near Beaune, on the 'route des Grands Crus' along the Côte de Nuits. This area is well known for its Grand Cru Burgundy wines, the most famous of which is Chambertin. <p>Objectives and key intervention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To develop a cost-efficient and rapid monitoring strategy based on rapid or on-line measurement of key parameters, with innovative tools: • IonSens Sensor from Olisens (OLI) to measure nitrates and chlorides (chloride is not a critical parameter for both DCs but Veolia France tested the parameter to help Olisens to get feedback on the measurement of chlorides with its prototype). • MetalSens from Olisens (OLI) to measure lead. • Bactosense sensor from bNovate (BNV) to measure total bacteria. • Udetect sensors from Orvion (ORV) for the measurement of the <i>E. coli</i> in raw and treated water. <p>Regarding MetalSens and IonSens, both current and forthcoming sensor deployments offer invaluable tools for efficiently managing treatment plants and distribution systems. These technologies provide rapid analyses with user-friendly portable equipment, facilitating sampling at various points from raw water sources to consumer taps. Consequently, Veolia can swiftly respond to fluctuations, particularly during sudden changes in meteorological conditions that may impact raw water quality.</p> <p>The last two sensors, Bactosense and Udetect (bacteriology) will undergo testing due to the critical importance of bacteriological parameters in the drinking water industry.</p>

ToDrinQ CS#4 - Beaune, France	
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beaune is served by the Bouzaise plant, which treats the raw water of the Bouzaise, coming from a karstic spring (source of the Bouzaise). Potential water quality issues are nitrates and pesticides (agriculture), hardness (karstic spring) and lead in the old parts of the distribution network. • In Gevrey-Chambertin, the Perrigny plant treats raw water from a well (superficial aquifer) and from a borehole that collects water from the South Dijon aquifer (deep aquifer). Potential water quality issues are nitrates, pesticides and hardness, along with total count of bacteria in tap water. <p>Water utilities can replicate the cost efficient and rapid monitoring of water, especially in the case of groundwater sources with variations in quality.</p>
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop robust real-time affordable sensors for water quality monitoring of the most sensitive parameters
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard sensors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #1: PestiSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5-6) • #2.1: MetalSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 6) • #2.2: IonSens (portable and online version, start TRL 3, expected TRL 6) • #3: Udetect semi-automatic (start TRL 3, end TRL 8) • #4: BactoSense (start TRL 3, end TRL 6-7) • #5: Concentration tool for microbiological sensors (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop sensors for rapid monitoring of key water quality aspects • Adjust water treatment for the elimination of pollutants even with variations in source (ground) water quality <p>Beyond the project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support continuous innovation in water quality monitoring
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drinking Water Directive 2020/184/EC <p>French legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The upper limits of Nitrates and Pesticides, in the French sanitary Code, are 50mg/l and 0.1µg/l per molecule for pesticides (or 0.5µg/l for the sum of all molecules analysed) respectively. If Veolia does not respect the level for Nitrates and Pesticides, the French sanitary government can stop the distribution system and Veolia would have to find other sources of drinkable water. Hardness should be adjusted at 18° to 20°F for both sites.
Policy implications	Use of hard sensors and soft sensors as alternatives for pre-described analytical methods in the European Drinking Water Directive
Market implications	Reinforcing contracts by guaranteeing water quality thanks to efficient treatment and monitoring

4.4.5. ToDriQ Case Study 5 - Prague, Czechia

ToDriQ CS#5 - Prague, Czechia	
	Managing upstream water quality variations and treating organic micropollutants in Eastern Europe
Location	Prague, Czech Republic
Pictures illustrating the case studies	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 4.4.5.1. Drinking water treatment plant. (© Veolia Holding Česká republika)</i></p>
Keywords	Drinking Water, water quality monitoring, pesticides, bacteria, heavy metals
Relevant climate change or pollution related challenges	The single raw water source (River Vltava) is subject to water quality variations due to upstream discharges of treated municipal and industrial wastewaters, and agricultural activities. Early detection of elevated concentrations of organic micropollutants compounds, such as pesticides, and metals is a challenge.
Current status of the case study:	This information summarises the current status (half way of the project duration of 4 years): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finished test of the of-line (laboratory) analysers for anions (nitrates, fluorides, chlorides...) • Finished test of the of-line (laboratory) analysers for metals (lead)
Key intervention and objectives	As part of the Prague Water Supply and Sewerage System the Prague, Podolí DWTP abstracts the raw water from the River Vltava which crosses the city of Prague and is prone to variations in flow and quality. The process train is composed of 3 steps of treatment with the GAC filtration recently added to enhance the removal of organic micropollutants and improve taste and odour. Field testing of 4 novel hardware sensors and 1 field water quality test-kit: PestiSens for pesticides (by OLISENS), IonSens for nitrates (OLISENS), MetalSens for (OLISENSE), BactoSense for total viable and non-viable bacteria (BNovate), UDetect field test-kit for E.coli detection by qPCR

ToDrinQ CS#5 - Prague, Czechia	
	(Orvion). All those water quality tools will be used at selected locations throughout the drinking water system, and also on the nanofiltration pilot unit for comparison with the full-scale GAC filters.
Scale & treatment, replicability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw surface water monitoring • Raw ground water monitoring • Water treatment line monitoring • Distribution network monitoring <p>Replication potential for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water utilities • Environmental agencies • Health state authorities
Expected outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get data for on-line analysers development • Improve quality of measurement of the of-line prototypes
Key technologies and deployment (TRL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard sensors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #1: PestiSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5-6) • #2.1: MetalSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 6) • #2.2: IonSens (start TRL 3, expected TRL 6) • #5: Concentration tool for microbiological sensors (start TRL 3, expected TRL 5)
Ambition at the end of the project and beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of cheap and competitive on-line analysers for effective drinking water quality monitoring • Based on the outcomes of the field testing and the actual return of experience the use of the most relevant water quality monitoring tools will be further deployed at other facilities operated by Veolia in Eastern Europe.
Key legislation and policies (EU / national / regional)	<p>European legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drinking Water Directive 2020/184/EC <p>Czech legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zákon 554/2020 Sb. • Zákon 167/2023 Sb. • And other legislation that deals with water and environment globally
Policy implications	Use of hard sensors and soft sensors as alternatives for pre-described analytical methods in the European Drinking Water Directive
Market implications	<p>Reinforcing contracts by guaranteeing water quality thanks to efficient treatment and monitoring by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving competition with existing producers of analytical equipment, e.g. by better pricing • Providing user references for reliable use of the sensors

5. Conclusions and outlook

Europe faces a structural gap in transferring technology to the market, leveraging the benefits for the society. By gathering similar cases, this document facilitates a comparative reading of the different options for the policymakers and key stakeholders who could deploy novel evidence-based and tested solutions towards a water-smart Europe in a resilient world.

This Case Study Inventory lists and describes the current state and the ambition of the 32 case studies of the seven ZeroPollution4Water Cluster projects. It provides a first structured overview about the characteristics of each case study to facilitate insights in common features of the case studies as well as in their different contexts and objectives. **Based on this initial Case Study Inventory similarities and differences between regions can be mapped.**

The cluster envisages that further work will allow to detect common challenges and address them in a more efficient way. Societal and technological innovations developed for one case study site may be transferred to other case studies and tested and validated in different environments. The Case Study Inventory will support the ZeroPollution4Water Cluster Working Groups in coordinating initiatives for the market uptake and exploitation of solutions and fostering the matchmaking between demand and offer.

Exploiting the synergies and differences of the 32 ZeroPollution4Water case studies will increase and consolidate the EU scientific and technological base on measures to manage groundwater and drinking water quality and provide evidence and guidance for policy-making and implementation.

The Inventory emphasises alignment with critical EU frameworks such as the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)¹³, Groundwater Directive (2006/118/EC)¹⁴, Drinking Water Directive (EU 2020/2184)¹⁵, and Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (98/15/EEC)¹⁶. These laws provide the foundation for improving groundwater and drinking water quality while addressing contaminants of emerging concern.

Looking at the guidance document for 2024-2029¹⁷ of the European Commission, this inventory could also contribute to the development of the **Water Resilience Strategy**.

It is important to underline that different case studies presented in this document point out several benefits for our society on the following elements:

- **Enhanced monitoring systems:** Adoption of cost-effective real-time monitoring technologies, including UV-VIS sensors, fluorescence tools, and bioreporters, could

¹³ European Commission. Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a framework for the Community action in the field of water policy; 2000/60/EC; 23 October 2000, **2000**; Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:5c835afb-2ec6-4577-bdf8-756d3d694eeb.0004.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.

¹⁴ European Commission. Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration. **2006**; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32006L0118>.

¹⁵ European Commission. Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (recast) (Text with EEA relevance), 2020; Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32020L2184>.

¹⁶ Commission Directive 98/15/EC of 27 February 1998 amending Council Directive 91/271/EEC with respect to certain requirements established in Annex I thereof (Text with EEA relevance). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31998L0015>; Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning urban wastewater treatment (Recast) of 27 November 2024; Available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/PE-85-2024-REV-1/en/pdf>

¹⁷ European Commission, Europe's Choice: Political Guidelines for the Next European Commission 2024-2029, European Commission, Brussels, 2024. https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/e6cd4328-673c-4e7a-8683-f63ffb2cf648_en?filename=Political%20Guidelines%202024-2029_EN.pdf.

ensure continuous assessment of water quality, early detection of pollutants, and adaptive management.

- **Nature-based solutions (NBS):** Promoting the application of NBS, such as constructed wetlands and phytoremediation, can offer sustainable and scalable water treatment methods, minimising pollutants and supporting aquifer recharge.
- **Climate resilience and adaptation:** Developing strategies to mitigate climate change impacts, including droughts, salinity intrusion, and extreme weather events, will ensure the robustness of water systems and safeguard their long-term sustainability.
- **Technology innovation and transferability:** Validating innovative technologies such as advanced filtration, AI-driven predictive models, and managed aquifer recharge systems in diverse case study environments will enhance their applicability across different EU regions.
- **Policy guidance and support for local regulatory framework:** The findings from these case studies can exchange best practices and support the development of water-smart local legislation and policies that prioritise water resilience, pollution prevention, and efficient water reuse practices.
- **Stakeholder engagement and public awareness:** Communication campaigns and Living Labs contribute to societal acceptance and facilitate the widespread adoption of innovative solutions and behaviours.
- **Data-driven decision support:** Employing advanced risk assessment tools and hydraulic models will improve operational efficiency, support real-time decision-making, and optimise resource allocation across water systems in line with digital water¹⁸ approach.

Next steps

To **enhance the ZeroPollution4Water Cluster's visibility and maximise the reach of its outcomes**, the projects will engage in various public events tailored to specific audiences. These events, including public webinars, workshops, and online gatherings under the banners of Water Project Europe, are designed to showcase the collective efforts and achievements of sister projects.

The **Policy Advisory Group** of the Cluster will develop a new set of policy recommendations focusing on groundwater and drinking water pollution challenges and addressing the upcoming Water Resilience Strategy.

Based on the case studies, the **Technology and Innovation Group** of the Cluster will assess the emerging technological and market potential, share best practices (based on case studies of the sister projects), and establish a roadmap for innovation and technology development for smart drinking water quality (IT-based) management (e.g. monitoring, risk assessment, modeling, prediction, and control).

The **Research and Innovation to Impact Working Group** of the Cluster will select and evaluate case studies from this inventory based on their potential to achieve pollution targets within the water sectors, considering their readiness for market deployment. The group will also evaluate the economic and regulatory challenges, using the PESTEL

¹⁸ Digital Water: exploit the benefits of the extreme interconnectivity of people, devices and processes, and create capillary networks capable of monitoring the water system, starting at its multiple sources through to the individual end user, thus generating continuous flows of valuable data for innovative decision-support systems at different governance levels ([Water Europe](#), 2023).

model (Political, Economic, Sociological, Technological, Legal, and Environmental) to navigate the legislative and competitive landscape.

At the beginning of each year, the Cluster opens a **Call for Interest for new projects** to join. These projects undergo an evaluation process to ensure alignment with the EU Zero Pollution Action Plan, further strengthening the Cluster's contribution to water pollution reduction on an annual basis.

ZeroPollution4Water Cluster Projects

	Project Acronym	Project number	Full title and website	Coordinator & contributors
1		101082048	MAR2PROTECT - Preventing groundwater contamination related to global and climate change through a holistic approach on managed aquifer recharge https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082048 ; https://mar2protect.eu	Ana B. Pereiro, Dario Frascati
2		101081865	NINFA - TakiNg actIoN to prevent and mitigate pollution oF groundwAter bodies https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081865 ; https://ninfa-project.eu	Ainhoa Gaudes
3		101081807	UPWATER - Understanding groundwater Pollution to protect and enhance WATER quality https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081807 ; https://www.upwater.eu	Enric Vazquez Suñé, Eike M. Thaysen
4		101081963	H2OforAll - Innovative Integrated Tools and Technologies to Protect and Treat Drinking Water from Disinfection By-products (DBPs) https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081963 ; https://h2oforall.eu	Rui Martins, Daniela Meilmann
5		101081728	intoDBP - Innovative tools to control organic matter and disinfection by-products in drinking water https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081728 ; https://intodbp.eu	Wolfgang Gernjak, Nuria Claramunt
6		101081980	SafeCREW - Climate-resilient management for safe disinfected and non-disinfected water supply systems https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081980 ; https://safecrew.org	Anissa Grieb, Margarete. Remmert-Rieper
7		101082035	ToDrinQ - TOolkit for aDaptable, Resilient INstallations securing high Quality drinking water https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082035 ; https://todrinq.eu	Luuk Rietveld, Danitsja van Heusden van Winden

List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence	ICT	Information and communications technology
AOC	Assimilable Organic Carbon	IR	Infrared
AOP	Advanced Oxidation Process	IT	Information and technology
ARB	Antibiotic resistant bacteria	LoRa	Long range
ARG	Antibiotic resistant genes	MABR	Membrane aeriated biofilm reactor
ATP	Adenosine-triphosphate	MAR	Managed aquifer recharge
ATR	Attenuated total reflection	MBBR	Moving bed biofilm reactor
BF	Bank filtrate	MFI-UF	Modified fouling index - ultrafiltration
BPA	Bisphenol A	MIR-FEWS	Mid-infrared fiberoptic evanescent wave sensor
CEC	Contaminants of emerging concern	ML	Machine Learning
CKB	Central Knowledge Base	MP	Microplastics
COD	Chemical oxygen demand	MS	Mass spectroscopy
CS	Case Study	MWW	Municipal waste water
DBP	Disinfection by-product	NBS	Nature-based solutions
DOC	Dissolved Organic Carbon	NOM	Natural Organic Matter
DOM	Dissolved Organic Matter	PAH	Polyaromatic hydrocarbons
DSS	Decision support system	PFAS	Per-and polyfluoroalkyl substances
DW	Drinking Water	QCRA	Quantitative Chemical Risk Assessment
DWD	EU Drinking Water Directive	QMRA	Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment
DWDN	Drinking Water Distribution Network	R&I	Research and Innovation
DWSS	Drinking Water Supply System	RAINREC	RAINfall-runoff RECharge re-distribution tool
DWTP	Drinking Water Treatment Plant	SUDS	Sustainable Drainage System
EU	European Union	THM	Trihalomethanes
FCM	Flow cytometry	TOC	Total organic carbon
FERT ROOT	FERTilizer use reduction through ROOT health enhancement	TRL	Technology readiness level
(G)AC	(Granular) Activated Carbon	TSS	Total suspended solids
GC-MS	Gas chromatography- mass spectrometry	UF	Ultrafiltration
GHG	Greenhouse Gas	UV	Ultraviolet
GLP	Good laboratory practice	WFD	Water Framework Directive
GW	Groundwater	WG	Working group
GWD	Groundwater Directive	WQP	Water quality parameter
HPLC-MS	High performance liquid chromatography – mass spectrometry	WSP	Water Safety Plans
HRMS	High resolution mass spectrometry	WW	Waste water
HRT	Hydraulic retention time	WWTP	Waste water treatment plants
HTC	Hydrothermal carbonisation	ZP4W	ZeroPollution4Water Cluster

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